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List of abbreviations

ACC	Accountability
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AUC	Area Under the receiver operating characteristic Curve
C-index	Concordance index
DnDF	Diversity, non-Discrimination and Fairness
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HAO	Human Agency and Oversight
HLEG-AI	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
PDG	Privacy and Data Governance
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SEW	Societal and Environmental Wellbeing
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TAI	Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
TPLC	Total product lifecycle
TPR	Transparency
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRS	Technical Robustness and Safety
UI/UX	User Interface / User Experience
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the updated version of the Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (AI) Development and Evaluation Framework for the AI-PROGNOSIS project. It builds upon the foundational version (D2.2 ‘Trustworthy AI development and evaluation framework (fundamental version)’) by incorporating new dimensions, updated practices, and consolidated technical reporting from all development partners. The framework continues to define core dimensions of trustworthy AI—such as robustness, generalisation, explainability, transparency, reproducibility, fairness, privacy, and accountability—while also introducing environmental sustainability as a new dimension. The updated version places significant emphasis on alignment with existing and emerging regulatory frameworks. It highlights adherence to the recently approved EU AI Act, incorporates best practices outlined in FDA guidance on AI-enabled medical devices, integrates the FUTURE-AI international consensus guidelines, and highlights ISO/IEC standards that are relevant to trustworthy AI development. Additionally, it promotes the use of the TRIPOD-AI checklist as a primary standard for transparent and comprehensive reporting of AI models in healthcare. In this updated version of the deliverable, we further elaborate the practices to be followed throughout the entire lifecycle of the AI-PROGNOSIS project. We specifically focus on best practices for clinician-facing explainable AI and the introduction of LLM-based explanation pathways. A new component on risk management has also been included, ensuring that risks are systematically identified, monitored, and addressed throughout the AI lifecycle. Also, this deliverable consolidates compliance reporting across model and application development partners, capturing implementation progress and future plan. Together, these updates provide a comprehensive, actionable, and forward-looking framework to guide the trustworthy development, evaluation, and deployment of AI tools in the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem and similar healthcare applications.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document scope

The core aim of AI-PROGNOSIS is to develop predictive Artificial Intelligence (AI) models for Parkinson's disease (PD) risk assessment and prognosis and build around them digital health tools to advance PD diagnosis and care. The mission of this deliverable is to shed light on the relevant recommendations, regulations and standards and utilise them as the basis for developing a guiding framework for building trustworthy AI tools in practice, with a focus on healthcare applications. Following this framework fosters trust-building in the development and utilisation of the AI systems, maximising therefore their positive impacts.

AI is increasingly being integrated into various parts of human life. People have begun to incorporate AI into their daily activities and expose their personal data. However, it is important to note that while current AI systems excel in performance, our primary goal should be the development of AI systems that are not only high-performing but also reliable and trustworthy. This is paramount for AI tools intended for healthcare purposes. Thus, the primary objective of this deliverable is to define the necessary steps for the development of trustworthy AI systems and to create a procedural framework that defines standards, procedures, tools, and metrics to be employed across the different phases of the AI system's lifecycle. Essentially, the framework serves as a guide for aligning the project's AI components with the principles of trustworthy AI. To ensure the comprehensiveness and effectiveness of the framework, it is built based on The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2020) requirements.

This deliverable (D2.6) builds on and updates the initial framework presented in D2.2 'Trustworthy AI development and evaluation framework (fundamental version)'. While D2.2 established the fundamental structure of the Trustworthy AI framework, D2.6 expands and refines it to reflect new regulatory developments, partner feedback, and additional alignment with international standards and guidelines. Major updates include: (i) new content on Green AI and environmental sustainability (Section 2); (ii) incorporation of the EU AI Act (2024) and FUTURE-AI consensus guideline; (iii) strengthened alignment with FDA guidance on AI-enabled medical devices and international ISO/IEC standards (Section 3); (iv) enhanced explainability pathways, including clinician-facing explanations and LLM-based methods (Section 4); (v) a comprehensive risk management system and file (Section 4.6.6); and (vi) a new compliance section (Section 5), to demonstrate adherence to the framework within AI-PROGNOSIS.

1.2 Document structure

The document begins with Section 1 as an introduction to provide an understanding of the AI-PROGNOSIS project and setting the stage for the framework and its importance. Following this, Section 2 includes a detailed section on the dimensions of trustworthy AI, incorporating insights from existing literature. Also, in that section, the socio-ethical aspects of trustworthy AI are highlighted emphasising on their effect on the development of the AI-PROGNOSIS project. Section 3 summarises the trustworthy requirements of existing guidelines and standards. Finally, Section 4, which is the core of the document looks into the specific components of AI development, aligning them with recognised guidelines and discussing methods to ensure the implementation of these components throughout the AI-PROGNOSIS project's lifecycle. Section 5 presents technical and compliance reporting, consolidating the implementation status, practices, and planned actions from model development partners.

Section 6 concludes the document and summarises the steps to be followed in the project for developing trustworthy AI tools.

2 Trustworthy AI foundation

Different research attempted to lay a definition of trust between humans and AI (Glikson & Woolley, 2020), (Jacovi et al., 2021), (Gillath et al., 2021). The main core ideas of these definitions are that trust in an AI system is the willingness of humans to engage and rely on the AI system, with a belief that the system will act in the human's best interest; thus, raising a sense of confidence in the positive outcomes of the AI system based on the understanding of its reliability and trustworthy intentions. The important dimensions or aspects of the AI system that emphasises its trustworthiness include robustness, generalisation, explainability, transparency, reproducibility, fairness, privacy preservation, and accountability (Li et al., 2023). To establish the foundation of our AI trustworthiness framework, we must carefully define these dimensions. It is worth mentioning that these trustworthiness characteristics are correlated and they influence each other. Also, it is worth noting that ensuring that all the trustworthy dimensions are applied to a certain AI system is less likely to be valid. Trade-offs between these dimensions take place in most cases. Thus, there is a significant need to reach a certain balance between these dimensions. This balance changes based on the problem we are addressing and based on the outcome of the AI system we intend to develop. In the updated version of the framework, we have also introduced environmental sustainability as a complementary dimension, reflecting recent trends in AI research and regulation that recognize the importance of energy efficiency and ecological responsibility as pillars of Trustworthy AI.

2.1 Defining trustworthy AI dimensions

In this section, definitions of the dimensions of AI trustworthiness will be presented. Moreover, relationships between certain dimensions will be highlighted. These definitions heavily rely on the ISO/IEC TS 5723:2022 (ISO/IEC, 2022) source that provides a definition of trustworthiness for systems and their associated services, along with a selected set of their characteristics.

2.1.1 Robustness

Robustness is the ability of a system to maintain its level of performance under a variety of circumstances. In general, robustness refers to an algorithm's capacity to sustain its performance even when exposed to diverse perturbations, adversarial inputs, erroneous data, or unseen data (Li et al., 2023). According to a systemic review that inspected key definitions of robustness and robust AI done by Tocchetti et al. (2023), two main robustness branches have been identified: robustness to adversarial attacks or perturbations, and robustness to natural perturbations. Adversarial attacks may include: a) decision-time attack that perturbs input samples during prediction to mislead the model, b) training-time attack (poisoning attack) that injects carefully designed samples into training data to alter the system's response to specific patterns, c) feature space attacks that are directly generated as input features of the model, d) problem space attacks that modify input entities to indirectly produce attack-related features, and e) model stealing (exploratory attack), which attempts to steal knowledge about models to generate adversarial samples without directly changing model behaviour (Li et al., 2023). While natural perturbation may be in the form of commonly witnessed natural noise, it is a condition more likely to occur in the real world compared to adversarial perturbations (Tocchetti et al., 2023).

2.1.2 Generalisation

Generalisation refers to the ability to derive knowledge from a limited training dataset to make accurate predictions when presented with new, previously unseen data. It encompasses the model's capacity to classify objects it was never initially trained on. The foundation of generalisation theory is the balance between underfitting and overfitting, with the goal of achieving a generalised model. Underfitting is also referred to as over-generalisation, which means that the Machine Learning (ML) model is trained in an extremely simple way, while if the model is extremely complex, it will not generalise well from observed data to unseen data (Ghojogh & Crowley, 2019). The notion of generalisation in AI closely intersects with other dimensions of AI trustworthiness, particularly its robustness. In ML, developing a robust model against shifts in data distribution negatively affects the generalisation of the model. Therefore, the robustness and generalisation dimensions have some overlapping aspects (Li et al., 2023).

2.1.3 Explainability

Explainability can be viewed as an active characteristic of a model, denoting any action or procedure taken by a model with the intent of clarifying or detailing its internal functions (Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020). Explainability is closely linked to the internal logic within a ML system. The greater the level of explainability in a model, the more understanding humans can gain in terms of the internal processes that occur during model training or decision-making. Understanding how an AI model reaches its decisions is an important factor in AI research and in increasing the trustworthiness of the AI system. From a scientific research perspective, having the knowledge about the essential mechanisms of data, parameters, procedures, and outcomes within an AI system, contributes significantly to the overall trustworthiness of AI systems.

In the field of ML, to offer an interpretable description of a model's behaviour, several actions can be taken. For example, sending all the model's parameter data or providing example predictions. Another approach involves summarising the components of the developed model in a tree-like explanation or giving information about the most influential features affecting the model's predictions. Each of these actions represents a potential means of explaining a complex model to the end user. The selection of these actions depends on both the application of the model and the intended end user. Model explainability focuses on developing inherently interpretable models and/or utilising *post-hoc* explainability methods. These techniques aim to explain the internal functions of ML systems, making them comprehensible to human understanding. *Post-hoc* explanation methods can either provide a global explanation of the entire black-box model or a local explanation that explains the individual predictions of the model and what are the factors impacting these predictions (Mahya & Fürnkranz, 2023). On the other hand, there are models that are considered to be explainable by themselves. For example, models like Linear/Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, K-Nearest Neighbours, and Bayesian Models have significant levels of inherent model explainability and require no additional post-hoc analysis (Barredo Arrieta et al., 2020).

2.1.4 Transparency and accountability

Transparency is the open, comprehensive, accessible, clear, and understandable presentation of information (ISO/IEC, 2022). Transparency has long been a recognised requirement in software engineering, requiring the disclosure of information about a system. In the AI industry, this essential principle covers the entire lifecycle of an AI system, allowing stakeholders to verify that appropriate design principles are met. To achieve transparency in the lifecycle of an AI system, different important information must be disclosed including design objectives, data sources, hardware specifications, configurations, operational conditions, anticipated usage patterns, and system performance metrics (Li et al., 2023).

Furthermore, a frequently raised query regarding AI regulation is to know the ways of taking advantage of what AI systems have to offer while ensuring that those who develop and use AI are held accountable. Accountability is a property that ensures that actions of an entity can be traced uniquely to the entity (ISO/IEC, 2022). In this context, accountability means the ability to determine if a decision adhered to both procedural and substantive criteria, and the capability to assign responsibility when these standards are not upheld (Joshua A. Kroll, Joanna Huey, Solon Barocas, Edward W. Felten, Joel R. Reidenberg, 2017). The main prerequisite of accountability is transparency. In other words, transparency serves as the primary mechanism enabling accountability in an AI system. It is worth noting that when taking actions to make AI systems more transparent and accountable, it is important to evaluate how these actions affect the organisation implementing these measures. Therefore, a balanced approach should be followed where transparency and accountability are improved without the disclosure of unnecessary resources or risking the exposure of valuable proprietary information (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023).

2.1.5 Reproducibility

Within the AI community, there is a significant concern about reproducibility among researchers and developers. Thus, reproducibility is a fundamental element of trustworthy AI. It signifies the ability for an independent researcher to reproduce either identical or reasonably similar results using the same data, code and settings that are followed by the original model developers. In addition to enabling the effective validation and verification of research in terms of its reliability, accuracy, and effectiveness of the results, reproducibility allows the community to implement latest approaches to conduct follow-up research. It also helps to ensure that the reported outcomes are not due to chance or specific circumstances, and it allows other researchers to build upon, validate, or improve upon existing AI work. It is important to mention that in the context of developing ML models, in particular Deep Learning models, reproducing results has become more challenging (Cockburn et al., 2020).

2.1.6 Fairness

Fairness is a common concern for AI practitioners. It represents a sociotechnical challenge that is important in avoiding the amplification of social biases within AI systems. While fairness and bias are related, they differ in scope: bias can be understood as a systematic deviation in data or model outputs from an expected, unbiased reference (Zliobaite, 2021), whereas fairness is a broader normative principle referring to the absence of discrimination or unequal treatment of individuals or groups on the basis of protected characteristics such as race, gender, age, or religion (Dwork et al., 2012). By definition, fairness in AI systems is incorporating concepts of equality and equity, aiming to address harmful bias and discrimination (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023). Achieving fairness in AI often involves approaches to mitigate bias rooted in protected or sensitive variables. These variables define aspects of data that are socio-culturally unsafe for the application of the AI system. Literature on fairness in AI emphasises two primary aspects: a) technical aspects, focusing on bias and fairness within the ML systems, and b) social, legal, and ethical theories, related to the discrimination in ML (Caton & Haas, 2023). Technical approaches to mitigate unfairness typically occur before, during, or after modelling (Binns, 2018). Pre-processing techniques recognise data biases (i.e., the distributions of specific sensitive or protected variables are imbalanced) and seek to rectify imbalances in distributions. In-processing methods recognise the tendency for the ML model to become biased by dominant features during the modelling phase. Post-processing strategies recognise whether the actual output of the ML model is potential unfair toward protected variables or subgroups within those variables. Therefore, prioritising fairness in AI demands a multifaceted approach that includes technical adjustments, as well as an understanding of broader social implications.

2.1.7 Privacy

Privacy is the freedom from intrusion into the private life or affairs of an individual (ISO/IEC, 2022). Privacy has a huge impact on AI trustworthiness, as it involves safeguarding data capable of identifying individuals or households, encompassing information like names, ages, genders, facial images, fingerprints, and more (Li et al., 2023). Privacy values, such as anonymity, confidentiality, and control, should inform decisions throughout the AI system's lifecycle, including design, development, and deployment. However, addressing privacy-related risks can affect other AI trustworthiness aspects like fairness and transparency, often requiring trade-offs among these characteristics. Furthermore, privacy-enhancing techniques, such as data sparsity, that contribute positively to enhancing the privacy of an AI system, can also result in a significant loss in its accuracy (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023).

2.1.8 Environmental sustainability (Green AI)

Green AI is an approach that aims to reduce the energy consumption and carbon footprint of AI systems, rather than only focusing on accuracy maximization (Verdecchia et al., 2023). It attempts to balance between model efficiency and environmental responsibility by promoting energy-efficient algorithms, hardware-aware designs, and minimum-resource usage, without reducing necessary performance (Bolón Canedo et al., 2024).

In recent literature, two complementary directions within Green AI are recognized: (1) Green-in-AI that focuses on the optimization of the internal workings of AI systems with methods such as sparse training, quantization, pruning, and low-precision arithmetic. This direction also leverages the use of hardware advancements like tensor processing units and edge computing to reduce the environmental impact of AI development and deployment. (2) Green-by-AI, refers to AI solutions for eco-friendly practices in other fields, such as smart mobility, climate change, or agriculture (Verdecchia et al., 2023). The EU's AI Act (approved in March 2024) focuses on establishing obligations for AI systems based on their potential risks and impacts, mandating environmental safeguards and sustainability reporting for high-risk AI systems. This regulatory framework highlights the growing role of both the green-in and green-by perspectives. In this context, Green AI intersects with the concept of Trustworthy AI by improving energy efficiency, it enhances sustainability, equity, and ethical responsibility. This is important particularly in vital sectors like healthcare that carries central concerns about resource constraints and regulatory compliance.

2.2 Socio-ethical dimension

Over the last decade, trustworthiness has emerged as one of the core pillars of ethical and responsible development in AI. In its prominent role, it has nonetheless received ample criticism in the literature on ethical and broader social impacts of AI. In the following subsection (Section 2.2.1), we will highlight the socio-ethical aspects of trustworthy AI as defined and outlined above (Section 2.1); we will then relay key criticisms of the overarching definition and focus on trustworthiness (Section 2.2.2); finally, we provide an update on how AI-PROGNOSIS has approached and updated the framework, and continues to address key concerns and as the project moves forward (Section 2.2.3).

2.2.1 Socio-ethical aspects of trustworthy AI

As outlined in Section 2.1, *Robustness* typically refers to an algorithm's capacity to sustain its performance even when exposed to diverse perturbations, adversarial inputs, erroneous data, or unseen data (ISO/IEC, 2022). Technical definitions can describe robustness, but they do not fully capture the lived experience of robust or non-robust AI implementation, which requires further probing. Crucially, natural perturbations involving unseen and/or erroneous data may

give rise to false positives and false negatives in diagnosis, inaccurate prognosis, and inadequate or directly harmful disease management protocol deployment. The implications of non-robust applications are therefore likely to harm users, as well as society at large. However, it should be noted that models considered robust may also be harmful, depending on how they are applied and used. Similarly, the *Generalisability* of the model(s) is, while a prerequisite for fair and equitable application, not a guarantee against harm to users. First, high generalisability of a model does not entail 100% success rate, meaning that over-reliance on the model(s) will inevitably risk harming outliers (Safdar et al., 2020). Furthermore, the robustness and generalisability of a model may prove harmful to end-users and society at large despite working as intended: while these features, i.e., robustness and generalisability, may support trustworthiness in terms of accuracy, they do not necessarily support trustworthiness with regard to key biomedical principles of ethics (e.g., beneficence, non-maleficence, and autonomy (Beauchamp T.L., 2001) or to facilitate trustworthy relationships between healthcare professionals, caregivers, and patients (Dalton-Brown, 2020)). This highlights the limits of robustness and generalisability as drivers of trustworthiness on a socio-ethical level, leading to the need for a broader understanding of trustworthiness as a comprehensive concept.

Explainability and *Transparency* pose further ethical and social challenges, particularly in contrast with Robustness and Generalisability. Now, it is a well-documented problem for AI development to balance the accuracy of a model against its explainability (London, 2019). While the severity of this conflict will chiefly depend upon model design and delivery (Hamon et al., 2020) (Rudin, 2019) (Lipton, 2018), the broader issue will likely remain in applications aimed at persons with little or no literacy in algorithmic model design. In order to deploy AI-powered applications, one needs to ask to whom those applications, or their results, are meant to be explainable and transparent. In AI-PROGNOSIS, and in projects like it, the challenge will be to allow for the data processing, output, and potential action plan suggestions to be transparent and explainable to a range of stakeholders, including health care professionals, professional and informal caregivers, patients, as well as persons whose risk of developing Parkinson's Disease is uncertain (Julie Gerlings, Millie Søndergaard Jensen, 2022) (Ehsan et al., 2021). The level and details of explainability shall be adapted based on the stakeholder.

How the principles of Explainability and Transparency are implemented will directly impact *Accountability* both within the system itself, and between the system and other agents. If a decision is (partially or wholly) made based on information presented by a model, or a set of models, where a clear rationale of that decision cannot be provided, accountability suffers, as it relies on agents acknowledging why a certain decision was made rather than another. In AI-PROGNOSIS, and other projects like it, the picture is complicated by the fact that there is not one, but multiple models and applications at play throughout the ecosystem, making oversight and appropriate accountability assignment more challenging: accountability in treatment management planning relies on not only its own transparency and explainability, but also on that of the prognosis of disease progression, which in turn relies on that of diagnosis. In this way, opacity (i.e., lack of explainability and transparency) is potentially contagious throughout the ecosystem as a whole, and care must be taken to not only ensure that each model and application in itself supports transparency and explainability, but to also implement measures to ensure that the complete ecosystem fosters it.

With regard to the principle of *Fairness*, much of AI development is currently occupied with minimising or erasing bias (Lin et al., 2021) (Trisha Mahoney, Kush R. Varshney, 2020). Even though that may be part of the implications on fairness, there is a broader set of problems of equality and equity at place, including issues surrounding access and capacity. On an institutional level, for instance, there are clinics, hospitals, and indeed whole healthcare

systems which are unlikely to be able to afford (or in other ways be prohibited from acquiring) and/or deploy an AI-powered ecosystem, such as AI-PROGNOSIS. Other institutions, while in principle able to acquire the system (as a whole, or parts of it), may lack the necessary capacity to train people or otherwise operate the system. Similar issues arise on an individual level, where persons – be they doctors or patients – may lack access to, or be incapable of operating, the relevant applications. When making design choices for systems such as those developed for AI-PROGNOSIS, care ought to be taken to allow fairness in dissemination and usability on a broader level.

Privacy, while often relatively clearly defined in steering guidance on AI development (ISO/IEC, 2022), will nonetheless be understood and practiced in a multitude of ways within and between any given society. Indeed, how privacy – and the safeguarding of it – should be understood and achieved in AI development, is a heavily debated topic (Murdoch, 2021) (Y. Zhang et al., 2021). As noted above (Section 2.1.7), in research and development the value of privacy may stand at odds with aims of transparency and accuracy within any given model. This issue becomes larger and more complicated as models are implemented: (1) in the field, where medical records, insurance, and other systems may be at play, and/or (2) together with other models which rely on the same principles of transparency, privacy, and accuracy. The challenge will be to balance what kind of data, how much of it, and in what ways will be share, from one stage of intervention (e.g., onset risk assessment) to the next (diagnosis, prognosis, treatment management). A related issue pertains to explainability, in the sense that it may prove difficult to disclose to users what type of data will be used, and in what ways, if it is not known exactly what that data are, and how they will be used. Similarly intertwined, privacy and data control have a direct impact on accountability, in that whoever controls a certain amount and type of data can only be held accountable for any privacy breach on the grounds that they are aware of what that data are, or indeed of that they are controlling them at all.

2.2.2 Socio-ethical criticisms of trustworthy AI

In reaction to the contemporary focus on developing AI to be Trustworthy, criticisms have emerged in the literature against this particular aim. The main criticisms can be divided into two categories.

The first category of criticism conveys the view that the concept of Trustworthiness is problematic, because the term “trust” and/or or the purported constituent dimensions – robustness, generalisation, explainability, transparency, reproducibility, fairness, privacy preservation, and accountability – are inadequately defined, or defined in conflicting ways across guidelines (Reinhardt, 2023) (AI, 2023) (Freiman, 2023) (Ryan, 2020).

The second category of critique highlights problems relating to the focus on Trustworthiness overall, and calls for a different and/or broader range of values to be accounted for and pursued (Rathkopf & Heinrichs, 2023) (Kerasidou et al., 2022). On a societal level, it is advisable to account for a multitude of understandings of key terms in Trustworthy AI (“trust” and “trustworthy”, but also “robust”, “transparent” and so on), but also to look beyond those key terms, and account for other values which may or may not be tied to the application AI models per se, but rather to that of interaction with a health-promoting system. Such values include (but not exclusively) the values of autonomy, relationship building and retention, sense of identity, and safety.

2.2.3 AI-PROGNOSIS, ethics and society: Updated analysis and strategy for socio-ethical impacts

This section outlines the revised socio-ethical strategy of AI-PROGNOSIS, structured around four key features. These features were originally introduced in the fundamental version of the

framework (D2.2) and are now revisited with implementation updates and strategic context. The four key features are:

- (1) Addressing relevant issues as identified by partners through assessment using the ALTAI framework. This will include the implementation of tools to measure adherence to key principles in each of the models and applications under development.
- (2) Allowing for the addition of complementary values to the framework – separate from “trustworthiness” and/or its constituent items – so to allow the pursuit of value-sensitive design and implementation across a range of domains, particularly in the domains of diagnosis, prognosis, and management of neurodegenerative disease, accounting for a broader range of ethical and social issues of pertinence to key stakeholders.
- (3) Anticipating and reacting to relevant policy landscape, to dynamically align with important guidelines and frameworks in this domain (see Section 3, **Table 1**).
- (4) Implementing mechanisms for oversight which guarantee the adherence to (1-3) above not only on a model-to-model or application-to-application basis but also allowing an overarching perspective on the potential ethical and social impacts of the project and its outcomes.

AI-PROGNOSIS set out to be guided by revised framework, defined by these four key features. The first and fourth of these features are ‘Addressing relevant issues as identified by partners through assessment using the ALTAI framework’, and ‘Implementing mechanisms for oversight’, respectively. As the project has progressed, the project has developed methods for measuring adherence to the models (applications are still under development), and these are outlined in greater detail in Sections 2 and 4 of this deliverable. Transparent and measurable adherence is crucial to establish trust and trustworthiness in the development phase, as adherence to ALTAI is a matter of internal analysis and self-reporting. These mechanisms will continue to be adhered to throughout the lifecycle of the individual models as well as the ecosystem as a whole

The second defining feature of the revised framework is allowing for the addition of complementary values to the framework. Notably, this component does not necessitate the addition of complementary values, but merely permits them. While no additional values have been found to affect the project as of yet, this feature plays an important role in at least two different ways – (1) procedurally (lit grounding and stakeholder engagement), and (2) substantively. (1) The feature to allow additional values [i.e. beyond those reflected by the standard Trustworthy AI (TAI) framework] was a response to a growing body of criticism of the TAI framework being too narrow (see 2.2 above), and it was decided that AI-PROGNOSIS should heed these concerns as a matter of methodological hygiene. For instance, this led to explicitly offering stakeholders of the co-creation workshops to express a wider range of ethical concerns about the models. Interestingly, the concerns raised without exception were deemed to fit neatly within the scope of the standard TAI framework. Nonetheless, this part of the process is procedurally important. (2) While no values obviously external to the TAI framework were uncovered through the initial co-creation workshops of AI-PROGNOSIS, there was no way of knowing this ahead of time. More importantly, it is not evidence that other projects may be different in this respect: small differences in aims, methods, outputs, or settings of other projects using AI for neurodegenerative diseases may very well uncover such non-TAI values at stake. In this way, the feature is substantively important. Hence, it will continue to be adhered to in AI-PROGNOSIS, and ought to be so also in other similar projects.

The third key feature of the revised trustworthy development and evaluation framework is ‘Anticipating and reacting to relevant policy landscape’. While this item is covered in greater

detail in Section 3 below, it is worth noting that the importance of this feature has come into full display since the first version of the trustworthy development and evaluation framework (D2.2). In June 2024, the EU adopted the Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AI Act), and full compliance across the union is expected within 24 months. In the meantime, a ban on systems posing ‘unacceptable risks’ was put into force by February 2025, and codes of practice have been applied since March 2025 (EU Parliament, 2025). Because of AI-PROGNOSIS readiness to anticipate the development and implementation of the EU AI Act, the project suffered no delays, but could react and adapt accordingly. This dynamic approach to the policy and legislative landscape will continue, as the project moves forward. This is particularly pertinent, as the EU has already signalled initiatives of deregulation – first through the ‘Communication on implementation and simplification’ (European Commission, 2025) and later through publicly stated commitments during the EU AI Summit to ‘cut red tape’ in the sector (von Der Leyen, 2025), followed by the scrapping of the AI Liability Directive draft. As AI-PROGNOSIS progresses towards finalisation, it is committed to not only continuously monitor the policy and legal landscape and react to it, but work in an anticipatory manner which allows for policy fluctuations. While D2.6 defines the final revised version of the trustworthy development and evaluation framework, project partners AING and UOXF will continue to lead on anticipating and monitoring the policy landscape, and on developing manuscripts for publication which reflect the project’s analyses of, and approach to navigating, that landscape. This will be crucial for addressing socio-ethical concerns in the final stages of model development, as well as in post-developmental (i.e., implementation) phases of the models, and of the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem as a whole.

3 Existing guidelines, standards, and regulations

Several frameworks and guidelines, as well as proposals, which highlight the principles for trustworthy AI systems and propose actions and requirements to raise trust between humans and AI systems have been developed and published by researchers, the industry, and policymakers in the recent past. **Table 1** summarises key aspects of a non-exhaustive list of important frameworks and guidelines related to trustworthy AI. This table is adopted from (Thiebes et al., 2021) and modified to include other relevant and important frameworks.

Table 1 Description of important frameworks and guidelines for trustworthy AI practices.

Framework/guidelines	Issued by (<i>in</i>)	Description
Asilomar AI Principles (Future of Life Institute, 2017)	Future of Life Institute (2017)	Describes 23 principles of beneficial AI. The principles are organised into three categories: research issues, ethics and values, and long-term issues.
Montreal Declaration of Responsible AI (Montreal Declaration) (University of Montreal, 2017)	Université de Montréal (2017)	Provides ten ethical principles that promote the fundamental interests of people and groups and, based on these, eight recommendations for the development of responsible AI.
UK AI Code (UK House of Lords, 2017)	UK House of Lords (2017)	Defines five overarching principles for an ethical AI code, intended to position the UK as a future leader in AI.

AI4People (Floridi et al., 2018)	Floridi et al. (2018)	A synthesis of six pertinent frameworks and guidelines, which resulted in five foundational principles for ethical AI. Based on the principles, a set of 20 action points in the four categories assessment, development, incentivisation, and support is proposed.
Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (EU TAI Guidelines) (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019)	European Commission Independent High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019)	Defines four principles of trustworthy AI and based on these derives seven key requirements for achieving trustworthy AI. Further provides an assessment list for the operationalisation of the seven key requirements.
OECD Principles on AI (The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 2019)	OECD (2019)	Recommends “five complementary values-based principles for the responsible stewardship of trustworthy AI” (OECD 2019). In addition to the OECD member states, other countries (e.g., Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Costa Rica, Peru, and Romania) have signed up to follow the OECD principles.
Governance Principles for the New Generation Artificial Intelligence (Chinese AI Principles) (National Governance Committee for the New Generation Artificial Intelligence, 2019)	Chinese National Governance Committee for the New Generation Artificial Intelligence (2019)	Provides a framework and action guidelines for the governance of AI, based on eight principles for the development of responsible AI.
White House AI Principles (Vought, 2020)	White House’s Office of Science and Technology Policy (Vought 2020)	Defines ten principles for stewardship of AI applications and the development of trustworthy AI. These principles are to be considered by US agencies during the development of regulatory and non-regulatory actions on AI.
Proposed Regulatory Framework for Modifications to Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML)-Based Software as a Medical Device (SaMD) - Discussion Paper and Request for Feedback (United States Food & Drug Administration, 2019)	U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) (2019)	Describes the FDA’s foundation for a potential approach to premarket review for artificial intelligence and ML-driven software modifications
The Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI) (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2020)	European Commission Independent High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2020)	Provides an initial approach for the evaluation of trustworthy AI based on seven high level requirements of trustworthy AI
Artificial Intelligence Act proposal (European	European Parliament, Council of the EU (2021)	The proposal presents a balanced and proportionate horizontal regulatory approach to AI that is limited to the minimum necessary

Parliament (Council of the European Union), 2021)		requirements to address the risks and problems linked to AI, without unduly constraining or hindering technological development or otherwise disproportionately increasing the cost of placing AI solutions on the market.
Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0) (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2023)	National Institute of Standards and Technology (2023)	Provides outcomes and actions that enable dialogue, understanding, and activities to manage AI risks and responsibly develop trustworthy AI systems. The Core is composed of four functions: GOVERN, MAP, MEASURE, and MANAGE
FUTURE-AI: international consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable artificial intelligence in healthcare (Lekadir et al., 2025)	FUTURE-AI Consortium	Provides six guiding principles—Fairness, Universality, Traceability, Usability, Robustness, and Explainability—developed via an international modified Delphi consensus. Offers clinically actionable recommendations to ensure AI systems are trustworthy and deployable in real-world healthcare

In this deliverable, the basis of the procedural trustworthy AI framework will be established based on the above-mentioned ALTAI tool, which is a cornerstone of the upcoming EU AI Act. In the following sections, a thorough review will be presented for the ALTAI requirements. Additionally, a comprehensive overview of other significant regulations, namely the AI Act and the EU-MDR, FDA, industrial guidelines, and ISO/IEC standards that will be allied along with the ALTAI requirements, is presented, forming a well-structured AI trustworthy framework.

3.1 ALTAI requirements

During the past years, the European Commission created the "High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence" (HLEG-AI) that published, in 2019, the "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019). These guidelines set out a framework that presents the EU's strategy for achieving trustworthy AI systems. It is stated that a trustworthy AI system has three main components:

- (1) It should be *lawful*, complying with all applicable laws and regulations. Several legally binding rules at both European and national level already apply or are relevant to the development, deployment and use of AI systems. Besides horizontally applicable rules, other domain-specific rules exist that apply to AI applications (such as the MDR in the healthcare sector and of course in the AI-PROGNOSIS case). The law provides rights as well as obligations. That means that these guidelines aim to offer guidance on fostering and securing the other two components (ethical and robust AI).
- (2) It should be *ethical*, ensuring adherence to ethical principles and values. Ethical norms and social cheques require adequate adoption and the alignment with the legal cheques as well. The ethical principles that should be taken into consideration are:
 - Respect for human autonomy
 - Prevention of harm
 - Fairness

- Explicability

(3) It should be *robust* both from a technical and social perspective. AI systems tend to be characterised as “egoistic” due to their extraordinary potential but even more so because of the excessive confidence people have in their abilities. The improvement of many different aspects of human’s life should be faced with a parallel awareness of the possible unintentional harm that those systems may cause. Robustness, security, and reliability should be ensured as well as safeguards should be foreseen to prevent any unintended adverse impacts. These requirements must be ensured both from a technical as well as a social perspective.

In addition, the HLEG-AI translated these components into seven concrete requirements that an AI system should take into consideration to achieve trustworthiness. These requirements are listed below and should be continuously evaluated throughout the whole AI life cycle as presented in **Figure 1**.

1. Human agency and oversight (HAO)
2. Technical robustness and safety (TRS)
3. Privacy and data governance (PDG)
4. Transparency (TPR)
5. Diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness (DnDF)
6. Societal and environmental wellbeing (SEW)
7. Accountability (ACC)

Figure 1 The seven trustworthiness requirements published by the HLEG-AI (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2019).

In the second half of 2019, the guidelines published by the HLEG-AI entered through a piloting phase, in which feedback was given by technical and non-technical stakeholders. Following this consultation period, in 2020, the HLEG-AI extended their guidelines and provided a self-assessment tool for the evaluation of the trustworthiness of an AI system. They published a document that contains the ALTAI (High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 2020)

for self-assessment. These supplementary guidelines set out the process to be followed in order to successfully proceed with an assessment on the development and operational characteristics of AI systems, with specific references to the procedures to be followed for any of the aforementioned requirements.

Furthermore, to show the functionality of this assessment list, the Vice-Chair of the AI HLEG and partners from the Insight Centre for Data Analytics at University College Cork implemented the ALTAI into a prototype web-based tool. This tool allows organisations to evaluate the trustworthiness of their AI system by answering a checklist online. This checklist is in the form of prompts and questions related to the seven guidelines published by the HLEG-AI and is aimed at providing practical assistance to AI developers and deployers by allowing them to easily evaluate the trustworthiness of their system. The output of the ALTAI web-based tool is a spider-diagram, as shown in **Figure 2**, assigns weights for each of the seven guidelines based on the organisation's responses during the self-assessment, as well as a list of the recommended steps the organisation can follow to improve their score.

Figure 2 An example of the spider diagram of the ALTAI web-based self-assessment tool.

It should be noted that the weights produced by the spider diagram reflect the number of recommendations. The HLEG, however, has not yet published how every response to the ALTAI questions influences the calculation of the overall weights presented in the spider diagram (Rajamäki et al., 2023).

3.1.1 Overview of the seven HLEG-AI requirements within the ALTAI tool

In this section, a comprehensive coverage of the sub-components addressed by ALTAI is presented, with each sub-component linked to the seven main requirements outlined earlier by HLEG-AI in Section 3.1 above.

3.1.1.1 Human agency and oversight (HAO)

The components of the HAO section aim to evaluate how thoroughly the subject organisation has utilised actions to address the impact of AI systems on human behaviour in various aspects including human decision-making processes, change of human perception and expectation when AI systems emulate human behaviour, and the impact on human emotions, trust, and autonomy. Additionally, the current requirement also refers to the human oversight factor which is also foreseen in the AI Act proposal and refers to the ability of the human to intervene in every decision cycle of the system. Therefore, some HAO components help organisations evaluate the level of consideration of oversight measures using governance mechanisms like human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, or human-in-command approaches.

Respect to the fundamental rights of the human beings during the operation process of the AI systems is of utmost importance. The developers and providers of the AI systems shall ensure that there will be no violation of the fundamental rights of their users and that the related provisions will be respected throughout the life cycle of the system. Respect to the human dignity is particularly ensured by providing all the necessary information to the user for him/her to be able to comprehend and interact with the AI system to a satisfactory degree, and by having full awareness that they are interacting with such systems, in order to be able to reach autonomous decisions regarding the AI system. The user shall be in a position to be able to reach to a decision following his/her intentions and thought process and not end up relying solely to the automatic processing operations of the AI system. The HAO components are listed in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Components of the human agency and oversight (HAO) requirement of the ALTAI.

HOA components
Incorporate a process where end-users and/or subjects are adequately made aware that an AI-system influenced the decision, content, advice, or outcome.
Ensure that the end-users or subjects are adequately informed that they are interacting with an AI system.
Put in place procedures to avoid that end users over-rely on the AI system.
Put in place any procedure to avoid that the system inadvertently affects human autonomy.
Take measures to deal with the possible negative consequences for end-users or subjects in case they develop attachment. In particular, provide means for the user to have control of the interactions.
Take measures to minimise the risk of addiction by involving experts from other disciplines such as psychology and social work.
Take measures to mitigate the risk of manipulation, including providing clear information about ownership and aims of the system, avoiding unjustified surveillance, and preserving autonomy and mental health of users.
Give specific training to humans (human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, human-in-command) on how to exercise oversight.
Establish detection and response mechanisms in case the AI system generates undesirable adverse effects for the end-user or subject.
Deploy a “stop button” or procedure to safely abort an operation when needed.
Take oversight and control measures to reflect the self-learning or autonomous nature of the AI system

3.1.1.2 Technical robustness and safety (TRS)

The TRS requirement is prioritised by the HLEG-AI in terms of the number of components which reflects its importance for building trustworthy AI systems. This requirement deals with

four main subsections that are the security, safety, accuracy; and reliability, fall-back plans and reproducibility. Components of the TRS requirement focus on utilising strategies to mitigate risks of intentional and unintentional harm caused by the AI system. These actions aim to increase the technical robustness of the system when exposed to adversarial changes, and to improve the dependability of the AI system by ensuring that it is delivering services and it is behaving reliably and as intended. The TRS components are listed in **Table 3**.

Table 3 Components of the technical robustness and safety (TRS) requirement of the ALTAI.

TRS components
Assess potential forms of attacks to which the AI system could be vulnerable.
Put in place measures to ensure the integrity, robustness and overall security of the AI system against potential attacks over its lifecycle.
Red-team/pen test the system
Inform users as soon as possible if some new threats are detected.
Define risk, risk metrics and risk levels of the AI system in each specific use case.
Identify the possible threats to the AI system (design faults, technical faults, environmental threats) and the possible resulting consequences.
Assess the risk of possible malicious use, misuse or inappropriate use of the AI system.
Assess the dependency of critical system's decisions on its stable and reliable behaviour.
Plan fault tolerance via, e.g., a duplicated system or another parallel system (AI-based or "conventional").
Develop a mechanism to evaluate when the AI system has been changed enough to merit a new review of its technical robustness and safety.
Put in place measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up to date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment the system will be deployed in.
Put in place a series of steps to monitor and document the AI system's accuracy.
Consider whether the AI system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adversarial effects (e.g., biased estimators, echo chambers etc.)
Put in place processes to ensure that the level of accuracy of the AI system to be expected by end-users and/or subjects is properly communicated.
Put in place a well-defined process to monitor if the AI system is meeting the goals of the intended applications.
Test whether specific contexts or conditions need to be taken into account to ensure reproducibility.
Put in place verification and validation methods and documentation (e.g., logging) to evaluate and ensure different aspects of the system's reliability and reproducibility.
Clearly document and operationalise processes for the testing and verification of the reliability and reproducibility of the AI system.
Define tested failsafe fallback plans to address AI system errors of whatever origin and put governance procedures in place to trigger them.
Put in place a proper procedure for handling the cases where the AI system yields results with a low confidence score.

Consider potential negative consequences from the AI system learning novel or unusual methods to score well on its objective function.

3.1.1.3 Privacy and data governance (PDG)

The components of the PDG refer to one of the fundamental rights, privacy. Respect for privacy and data protection, quality, integrity, and access to data should be ensured during the development and, most crucially, the operation of the AI system. Compliance with the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the applicable complementary national privacy-related legislation shall be ensured and the developer of an AI system shall comply with all the responsibilities related to the assurance of privacy and personal data integrity. The PDG components encourage organisations to implement actions that ensure the integration of the right to privacy and data protection in the design process of AI systems. The PDG components are listed in **Table 4**.

Table 4 Components of the privacy and data governance (PDG) requirement of the ALTAI.

PDG components
Take measures to consider the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy, the right to physical, mental and/or moral integrity and the right to data protection.
Consider establishing mechanisms that allow flagging issues related to privacy or data protection concerning the AI system.
When relevant, implement the right to withdraw consent, the right to object and the right to be forgotten in the AI system.
Consider the privacy and data protection implications of data collected, generated or processed over the course of the AI system's lifecycle.
Consider the privacy and data protection implications of the AI system's non-personal training-data or other processed non-personal data.
Whenever possible and relevant, align the AI system with relevant standards (e.g., ISO, IEEE) or widely adopted protocols for (daily) data management and governance.

3.1.1.4 Transparency (TPR)

The TPR requirement and its components mainly deal with the general idea of the explainability dimension within trustworthy AI systems, as defined in Section 2.1.3. The first element of this requirement is traceability, in which organisations are encouraged to consider a proper documentation strategy about methods used to design and develop the algorithmic system, the methods used to test and validate it, as well as the outcomes of the algorithmic system. The second element is explainability, that is tackled by ensuring that the decisions of the AI system are well understood by those directly and indirectly affected by it. The third element is communication, focusing on the importance of informing users about the limitation of AI-based decisions. The TPR components are listed in **Table 5**.

Table 5 Components of the TPR requirement of the ALTAI.

TPR components
Consider adopting measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system.
Consider adopting adequate logging practices in place to record the decision(s) or recommendation(s) of the AI system
Consider explaining the decision adopted or suggested by the AI system to its end users.

Consider continuously surveying the users to ask them whether they understand the decision(s) of the AI system.
In case of interactive AI system, consider communicating to users that they are interacting with a machine.
Establish mechanisms to inform users about the purpose, criteria and limitations of the decision(s) generated by the AI system

3.1.1.5 Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness (DnDF)

As TRS, the DnDF requirement contains a significant number of components that are set by the HLEG-AI that are aimed at fostering fairness and inclusivity within AI systems. The components of the DnDF requirement focus on the importance of utilising strategies to mitigate bias in input data and AI algorithm design. Moreover, DnDF components aim to prioritise user inclusivity by ensuring that AI products or services are accessible to individuals of all ages, genders, abilities, or characteristics. The DnDF components are listed in **Table 6**.

Table 6 Components of the diversity, non-discrimination, and fairness (DnDF) requirement of the ALTAI.

DnDF components
Consider establishing a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design.
Consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data.
Test for specific target groups or problematic use cases.
Research and use publicly available technical tools, that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance.
Assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system (e.g., biases due to possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets (lack of diversity, non-representativeness)).
Consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data.
Put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system.
Depending on the use case, ensure a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system.
You should establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised.
Identify the subjects that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end)-users.
Your definition of fairness should be commonly used and should be implemented in any phase of the process of setting up the AI system.
Consider other definitions of fairness before choosing one.
Consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of fairness, such as representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities.
Ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness.
Establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI system.
You should ensure that the AI system corresponds to the variety of preferences and abilities in society.

You should assess whether the AI system's user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion.
You should ensure that Universal Design principles are taken into account during every step of the planning and development process, if applicable.
You should take the impact of the AI system on the potential end-users and/or subjects into account.
You should assess whether the team involved in building the AI system engaged with the possible target end-users and/or subjects.
You should assess whether there could be groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the system.
You should assess the risk of the possible unfairness of the system onto the end-user's or subject's communities.
You should consider a mechanism to include the participation of the widest range of possible stakeholders in the AI system's design and development.

3.1.1.6 Societal and environmental wellbeing (SEW)

HLEG-AI considered SEW as a requirement for building a trustworthy AI system. SEW is composed of three elements. First, the environmental well-being element, which focuses on the potential impacts of the AI system on the environment. Second, the "Impact on Work and Skills" element, that involves components that focus on the influence and usage of the AI system within work environments. Furthermore, the SEW requirement covers the "Impact on Society at Large or Democracy" element that considers the effects of the AI system on institutions, democracy, and the overall fabric of society. The SEW components are listed in **Table 7**.

Table 7 Components of the societal and environmental wellbeing (SEW) requirement of the ALTAI.

SEW components
Consider the potential positive and negative impacts of your AI system on the environment and establish mechanisms to evaluate this impact.
Define measures to reduce the environmental impact of your AI system's lifecycle and participate in competitions for the development of AI solutions that tackle this problem.
Inform and consult with the impacted workers and their representatives but also involve other stakeholders. Implement communication, education, and training at operational and management level.
Take measures to ensure that the work impacts of the AI system are well understood on the basis of an analysis of the work processes and the whole socio-technical system.
Take measures to counteract de-skilling by means of continuous training, especially in areas sensitive in terms of safety and security.
Provide training opportunities and materials for re- and up-skilling measures.
Assess the societal impact of the AI system's use beyond the (end-)user and subject, such as potentially indirectly affected stakeholders or society at large.
Take actions to minimise potential societal harm of the AI system.
Take measures that ensure that the AI system does not negatively impact democracy.

3.1.1.7 Accountability (ACC)

The ACC requirement set by HLEG-AI contains components to establish mechanisms that facilitate the system's auditability, focusing on reporting and minimising negative effects, as well as components for training and education to help develop accountability practices and

establishing processes for third parties or workers to report such vulnerabilities, especially in applications affecting fundamental rights and safety-critical areas. Furthermore, the components highlight the risk management element of the requirement by encouraging organisations to consider reporting on actions or decisions contributing to outcomes and to manage the consequences, especially for those directly or indirectly affected by the AI system. The ACC components are listed in **Table 8**.

Table 8 Components of the accountability (ACC) requirement of the ALTAI.

ACC components
Establish mechanisms that facilitate the AI system's auditability (e.g., traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system's processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact).
Ensure that the AI system can be audited by independent third parties.
Foresee any kind of external guidance or third-party auditing processes to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures.
Organise risk training for developers and deployers to inform them about the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system.
Establishing an AI ethics review board or a similar mechanism to discuss the overall accountability and ethics practices, including potential unclear grey areas.
Establish a process to discuss and continuously monitor and assess the AI system's adherence to this Assessment List for Trustworthy AI.
Establish a process for third parties (e.g., suppliers, end-users, subjects, distributors/vendors or workers) to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system.
Ensure that redress-by-design mechanisms are put in place for applications that can adversely affect individuals.

3.2 AI Act

The AI solutions of AI-PROGNOSIS, developed within the regulatory framework of the European Union, must adhere to the provisions of the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act) (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689), which introduces a comprehensive, risk-based approach to the regulation of artificial intelligence. Given that AI-PROGNOSIS involves clinical research, sensor-based data collection, mobile health applications and predictive AI functionalities, it is essential to assess the risk categorisation of the AI systems integrated into the project, determine their regulatory implications and outline the compliance obligations that apply.

The AI Act distinguishes four categories of risk: prohibited AI systems, high-risk AI systems, limited-risk AI systems and minimal-risk AI systems.

Elements of the project may fall under the "high-risk" category as defined in Title III of the AI Act. In particular, AI systems that are intended to be used in healthcare settings and that influence clinical decision-making or assist in the prediction of disease progression are likely to be classified as high-risk. The mAI-Health, mAI-Care and mAI-Insights components of AI-PROGNOSIS collect and process biometric data, sensor data and medical information in a way that may affect medical judgments. Where these systems are used in support of diagnosis or treatment, they may be considered high-risk, especially if integrated with or used in conjunction with certified medical devices regulated under the Medical Device Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2017/745).

As such, AI-PROGNOSIS will be subject to obligations including the implementation of appropriate risk management systems (Article 9), data governance measures ensuring the quality of datasets used to train the AI models (Article 10), detailed technical documentation (Article 11), maintenance of record-keeping for traceability (Article 12), activation of human oversight protocols (Article 14), insurance of robustness, cybersecurity, accuracy and transparency to deployers (Articles 13–15). Where applicable, conformity assessments will be carried out in accordance with Annex II or Annex III of the AI Act before placing the systems on the market or putting them into service.

In addition to high-risk AI, certain components of AI-PROGNOSIS may be classified as limited-risk systems. Under Title IV of the AI Act, AI systems that interact with humans or generate synthetic content, must comply with transparency obligations. The mAI-Insights and mAI-Care applications, to the extent that they interface with users and provide feedback or guidance, are required to inform users that they are interacting with an AI system, pursuant to Article 52 of the AI Act.

Finally, certain tools within the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem may fall within the minimal-risk category, such as administrative analytics or internal reporting modules that do not affect the rights or safety of individuals. These components do not attract specific regulatory requirements under the AI Act.

To ensure conformity with the AI Act, the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium has adopted a series of technical and organisational safeguards. These include procedures for data minimisation, pseudonymisation and access control, implemented across the data management system, i.e., both the Hetzner Cloud infrastructure (see also D4.3 ‘Updated technical specifications, architecture and product backlog’) and partners’ premises. All high-risk systems incorporate human oversight mechanisms and are designed to prevent automation bias in clinical decision-making. The project will also conduct a risk assessment aligned with Article 29 of the AI Act and supplement existing Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) under the GDPR.

Transparency requirements are addressed by integrating user-intended content and disclaimers within the AI interfaces, ensuring participants are adequately informed about the AI-based nature of the tools and their role in data processing and decision support. Informed consent processes have been structured to encompass the use of AI technologies, in accordance with both the AI Act and Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR.

It is important to note that the tools are currently in the clinical study phase, during which they do not provide direct feedback to study participants or influence clinicians’ decisions. Instead, their function is limited to collecting data that serve as input to predictive models and digital biomarker pipelines the output of which will be compared with clinical assessments for proof-of-concept validation. A definitive conclusion regarding the final Minimum Viable Products (MVPs) of the project and its classification under the AI Act will be provided in the final version of D6.7 ‘Exploitation and Regulatory Approval Plan’.

In anticipation of potential future deployment of AI-PROGNOSIS components in clinical or commercial settings, the project will ensure that all high-risk AI systems are subject to pre-market conformity assessments where required. Technical documentation and relevant policies will be regularly reviewed and updated in line with emerging guidance from EU authorities and regulatory bodies. The project will also consider engagement with notified bodies to clarify classification and certification obligations should its tools transition to regulated medical applications.

Through these measures, AI-PROGNOSIS aims to ensure lawful, ethical and transparent deployment of AI technologies in line with the AI Act.

3.3 Regulatory compliance and risk management for AI in medical devices

High-risk AI systems related to products, such as medical devices, are described by the New Legislative Framework (NLF). For the AI-PROGNOSIS medical devices, the requirements for AI systems set out in the AI Act are checked as part of the existing conformity assessment procedures under the relevant “Medical devices - Regulation (EU) 2017/745 (MDR)” (European Parliament (Council of the European Union), 2017). If a medical device that operates on AI or contains AI elements falls within Risk Class IIa or higher (the classification of medical devices is based on their intended purpose and their inherent risks, as set out in Annex VIII of the MDR) and, as a result, a notified body is to be involved in the conformity assessment procedures, this medical device is a high-risk AI system within the meaning of the AI Act.

The rules concerning how the independent notified bodies that assess the conformity of medium and high-risk medical devices before they are placed on the market, have become stricter and are designated, organised and monitored.

With the AI Act now in force, given that a medical device is considered as high-risk AI system, there are some specific requirements with which compliance should be ensured. Among others:

- A risk management system shall be established, documented, and maintained which shall consist of a continuous iterative process run throughout the entire lifecycle of the high-risk AI system, requiring regular systematic updating.
- Data and data governance principles should also be considered, as well as the continuously updated technical documentation that should be drawn up before that system is placed on the market or put into service.
- Another aspect that is set as a prerequisite for the trustworthiness of the high-risk AI systems, is the record keeping of logs during the operation of the AI system. These logging capabilities shall conform to recognised standards or common specifications. These capabilities shall ensure a level of traceability of the AI system’s operation throughout its lifecycle that is appropriate to the intended purpose of the system.
- Transparency, accuracy, robustness, and provision of information for users is also needed so that AI systems are concise, complete, correct and easily accessible to users.
- Human supervision during the period in which the AI system is in use aiming at preventing or at least minimising the risks to health, safety and fundamental rights that may emerge when a high-risk AI system is used in accordance with its intended purpose or under conditions of reasonably foreseeable misuse. It is important to note that human supervision should be ensured before the AI system is placed on the market or put into service to prevent incidents like automation bias. All principles and requirements should be translated into obligations for providers and users of high-risk AI systems, to ensure their compliance with them and to be able to contact the relevant notified bodies whenever necessary. The forementioned applies in a less extent to importers and distributors.

Compared to the MDR, the AI Act introduces additional requirements, so it is quite expected that this will result as a considerable burden for developers of such technologies in the

conformity assessment procedure. There are already numerous requirements and obligations in the regulation for the medical devices, which include among others, requirements for risk management systems and documentation. The overlap of requirements though between the MDR and the AI regulation in some places is to be resolved by subjecting the safety risks of AI systems to the requirements of the AI Act, while the safety of the product as a whole will be assessed under the MDR.

More specifically in article 43 of the AI Act, various conformity assessment procedures for high-risk AI systems are regulated. Providers of high-risk AI systems must prove that they meet the requirements according to the regulation. The provider must therefore follow the relevant conformity assessment procedures under MDR. The Notified Bodies designated under the MDR shall also be entitled to check the conformity of high-risk AI systems with the requirements of the draft Regulation and thus be able to constitute a “notified body” within the meaning of the draft Regulation. As a result, it is still necessary to carry out only one single conformity assessment procedure for AI medical devices in accordance with the requirements of the MDR, which must additionally ensure compliance with the requirements of the draft regulation. However, notified bodies must have sufficient internal competence to effectively assess the tasks performed by external bodies on their behalf. In this respect, all parties involved must ensure at an early stage that, in addition to the requirements of the MDR for medical devices – and in particular the software that falls under them - those of the future regulation that exceed these are observed. It must be checked whether the AI used meets the safety requirements, while internal processes and products are adapted accordingly.

Comparing the MDR and the AI Act, it is evident that there are key differences between the two regulations and that the AI Act seeks to address specific risks inherent to AI systems. The classification of the MDR into different risk levels based on the intended purpose of the medical device is treated differently in the AI Act, which generally designates AI systems governed by the MDR as high-risk. While conformity assessment remains a prerequisite under both frameworks, the AI Act introduces additional obligations, requiring ongoing assessment before, during and after the development lifecycle of high-risk AI systems. Moreover, the AI Act explicitly mandates human oversight as a risk management measure and imposes stricter requirements regarding data quality, including relevance, representativeness, completeness and the absence of errors. Medical devices incorporating machine learning (ML) components must therefore comply with both regimes. ML-based systems, unlike static rules-based software, are adaptive and data-driven, which introduces added complexity in terms of transparency, risk monitoring and accountability. Manufacturers must now align technical documentation, post-market surveillance, and risk management systems to meet the combined expectations of both the MDR and the AI Act.

Finally, there are also certain harmonised standards, relevant to the development and distribution of medical devices, linking both MDR and the AI Act. The MDR allows proof of conformity to be provided with the aid of harmonised standards and common specifications such as:

- ISO 13485:2016: Medical devices - Quality management systems - Requirements for regulatory purposes (ISO, 2016)
- IEC 62304: Medical device software - Software life-cycle processes (IEC, 2006)
- IEC 62366-1: Medical devices — Part 1: Application of usability engineering to medical devices (IEC, 2015)
- ISO 14971: Medical devices — Application of risk management to medical devices (ISO, 2019)

- IEC 82304: Health software - Part 1: General requirements for product safety (IEC, 2016)

While these standards are not legally binding in a strict sense, they serve as essential guidelines to promote the safe development and operation of medical devices. They define key requirements related to documentation, lifecycle management, and risk control. By outlining appropriate procedures, these standards help ensure both the secure functioning of medical devices and compliance with regulatory expectations.

3.4 Responsible AI pillars in the industry

It is important to mention the AI pillars of leading companies in the industry that utilise AI, including IBM¹, Google², and Meta³. These companies present their responsible AI principles with distinct emphases, but share common ethical themes as those in the EU's ALTAI framework.

- IBM focuses on explainability, fairness, robustness, transparency, and privacy, underlining the importance of trust, transparency, and ethical principles at the core of AI development.
- Google emphasises a human-centred design approach, consideration of adverse feedback, diverse user engagement, and rigorous testing, highlighting practical steps towards fairness, safety, and usability.
- Meta outlines pillars including privacy and security, fairness and inclusion, robustness and safety, transparency and control, and accountability and governance, stressing the need for systems that are equitable, secure, and accountable.

These pillars collectively underscore a commitment to developing AI that is ethical, secure, fair, and transparent, mirroring ALTAI's focus on trustworthiness within its seven concrete requirements explained in section 3.1.

3.5 FDA guidance on lifecycle management of AI-enabled medical devices

In addition to EU guidelines and regulations, the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA), recently published guidance on the lifecycle management of AI-enabled medical devices, giving valuable recommendations for the responsible design of such technologies. The FDA's draft guidance document "Artificial Intelligence-Enabled Device Software Functions: Lifecycle Management and Marketing Submission Recommendations" (2023) outlines important principles and best practices of safety, efficacy, and transparency in medical device software based on AI.

The FDA's draft guidance emphasizes a robust, total product lifecycle (TPLC) approach to managing AI-enabled medical devices. It aims to ensure these devices' safety, effectiveness, transparency, and fairness across all demographic groups. Key elements highlighted in the draft include:

1. **Lifecycle management:** The FDA recommends TPLC, which ensures continued regulatory oversight across the development through deployment phase and after-market

¹ IBM. [IBM Artificial Intelligence Pillars - IBM Policy](#)

² Google. [Google Responsible AI Practices – Google AI](#)

³ Meta. [Responsible AI - AI at Meta](#)

monitoring. Recommendations also include systematic risk assessment, robust data management, and careful consideration of the dynamic nature of models in AI.

2. **Transparency and bias mitigation:** Transparency is also central, emphasizing on clear information about the function of the AI device, including user interface and labelling (the essential information about a device's purpose, usage, risks, and maintenance). Moreover, methods for minimizing and control of bias are also emphasized by focusing on the importance of using representative data collection to ensure equitable performance across demographic subgroups (age, sex, ethnicity, race).
3. **Data management:** The guideline focuses on appropriate data quality, representativeness, and proper data management practices. Explicit description of the characteristics of the datasets, preprocessing methods, and validation strategies is recommended by the FDA.
4. **Performance validation:** The FDA stresses that evaluating device performance across the overall population is not enough—subgroup analysis (e.g., by demographics or disease subtype) is essential to identify disparities that may not be visible in aggregated results. Subgroup validation not only enhances safety and equity but also supports transparent labelling, helping end users understand limitations and appropriate use cases. Additionally, FDA emphasizes the importance of addressing uncertainty in model outputs as it helps reviewers understand how to interpret device outputs
5. **Risk management:** There must be an adequate risk analysis to demonstrate safety and efficacy for an AI-enabled device. Sponsors must integrate a risk management file (plan, assessment, and report). For the specific issues of AI in particular, the FDA recommends referring to the AAMI CR34971 (ISO, 2019), which covers unique risks for AI and machine learning. Also, the FDA highlights that usability and transparency of information must be important elements of risk management for products based on AI and that addressing these risks is integral to maintain user trust.
6. **User interface and labelling:** To ensure effective and safe use of AI-enabled medical devices, FDA recommends the design of the user interface to display important information about the device use stages (including setup, use, and maintenance) so users can obtain timely, context-aware advice. In addition to traditional labelling, risk information should be displayed in dynamic formats such as on-screen alerts, device notices, and related product interfaces to establish user awareness and mitigate potential risks. AI-enabled devices, labelling should specifically describe the model type, model performance characteristics, and type of training data used in transparent detail to allow the user to foresee device behaviour and factors that affect its functionality. Furthermore, the inclusion of model card in the labelling is also advised to give transparent, structured information of what the AI model does along with the model strengths, limitations, and appropriate use cases.
7. **Cybersecurity considerations:** FDA recommends that sponsors align with the 2023 Premarket Cybersecurity Guidance⁴, which outlines key objectives including authenticity, authorization, availability, confidentiality, and the secure and timely updatability or patchability of software. Cybersecurity risks specific to AI must be taken into consideration, such as data poisoning, model inversion or stealing, model evasion, data leakage, deliberate overfitting, manipulation of model bias, and performance drift. To address these threats, cybersecurity risk management documentation tailored to the AI components of

U.S. Food and Drug Administration (2023). *Cybersecurity in Medical Devices: Quality System Considerations and Content of Premarket Submissions*. <https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/cybersecurity-medical-devices-quality-system-considerations-and-content-premarket-submissions>

the device should be provided, including results from essential security testing procedures such as fuzz testing (to assess resilience against malformed inputs) and penetration testing (to evaluate exploitability). Additionally, strong data protection controls must be implemented and clearly documented, including robust access control mechanisms, encryption practices, and the anonymization or de-identification of sensitive or personally identifiable information.

The FDA's emphasis on transparency, bias mitigation, rigorous validation, and AI lifecycle oversight is consistent with the Trustworthy AI principles of the AI-PROGNOSIS project. Utilization of these best practices—where possible—further increases the strength and adaptability of our framework. In this updated version, we also introduced Section 4.6.6 (Risk management system and file), aligning directly with FDA's TPLC and AAMI CR34971 guidance for AI-specific risk management. As the project advances toward regulatory alignment, staying apprised of global regulatory directions such as the FDA's benefits the broader foundation for responsible, cross-jurisdictional innovation in healthcare AI. To demonstrate how these recommendations are operationalized in our work, **Table 9** below maps each of the FDA's key areas to the relevant subsections of our AI-PROGNOSIS framework (Section 4).

Table 9 Alignment of FDA lifecycle recommendations with AI-PROGNOSIS framework (Section 4).

FDA recommendation	AI-PROGNOSIS framework sections
Lifecycle management	4.6.1 Model Operations; 4.6.2 Model and dataset reporting; 4.6.5 Sustainability and societal impact; 4.6.6 Risk management system and file
Transparency & bias mitigation	4.1.2 Explainability tailored to each user; 4.1.3 Fairness goals & protected attributes; 4.2.3 Data quality & bias identification; 4.5.1 Diversity & non-discrimination in clinical studies
Data management	4.2.1 Outlier detection & data sanitisation; 4.2.2 Pseudonymisation/anonymisation; 4.2.3 Data quality & bias identification
Performance validation	4.3.3 Performance benchmarking; 4.3.5 Uncertainty benchmarking; 4.5.1 Diversity in clinical validation
Risk management	4.6.6 Risk management system and file; 4.3.7 Performance–privacy trade-off; 4.6.4 Security & GDPR compliance
User interface & labelling	4.4.7 Explanation of models & outputs; 4.4.8 Educational content on AI; 4.6.2 Model & dataset reporting
Cybersecurity considerations	4.6.4 Security & GDPR compliance; 4.4.2 Adversarial testing; 4.6.1 Model Operations; 4.6.6 Risk management system and file

3.6 ISO/IEC Standards for Trustworthy AI development

International standardization efforts, particularly those led by ISO and IEC, enrich the foundation for trustworthy AI development. These standards cover conceptual, technical, and organizational dimensions, that align closely with frameworks such as the EU AI Act, the ALTAI principles and FDA guidelines. This section surveys key ISO/IEC standards for trustworthy AI. We focus on general trustworthiness practices across the entire AI lifecycle (from data management and model development to validation, deployment, and post-market monitoring), aligned with principles from frameworks like the EU's ALTAI guidelines and the EU AI Act. The ISO and IEC standards represent a complementary toolset that covers all elements of trustworthy AI development. **Table 10** compiles a brief description to the related

standards and its relevance to trustworthy AI practices across the AI lifecycle, with a focus on how their principles are reflected in Section 4 of our framework.

Table 10 Summary of key ISO/IEC standards and their relevance to trustworthy AI development

Standard / Report	Trustworthy AI focus & contributions	Reflected in AI-PROGNOSIS framework (Section 4)
ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 (Overview of trustworthiness in AI) ⁵	It encompasses all aspects of AI trustworthiness – transparency, explainability, bias, robustness, safety, security, and privacy – and discusses protection and mitigation methods against vulnerabilities. It provides a high-level overview of best practices to increase trust in AI systems (in alignment with ALTAI principles like transparency, accountability, and robustness). It also gives context to additional standards by specifying key areas of trust throughout the AI lifecycle.	Section 4.1 (design & specification of explainability, fairness goals); 4.3 (robustness & uncertainty benchmarking); 4.6 (security & monitoring).
ISO/IEC 5338:2023 (AI lifecycle processes) ⁶	Defines a complete lifecycle model for AI systems. Covers inception, design & development, verification & validation, deployment, operation & monitoring, continuous validation, re-evaluation, and retirement.	The structure of Section 4 was directly influenced by ISO/IEC 5338.
ISO/IEC23894:2023 (Guidance on risk management) ⁷	It offers a systematic risk management process for AI such that organizations can identify, assess, and contain AI-related risks throughout development and deployment. It is compliant with ISO 31000 principles and provides AI-specific risk scenarios. It supports safety, reliability, and responsibility through implementation of continuous risk assessment (meeting EU AI Act requirements for risk management).	Section 4.6.6 Risk management system & file (plan, assessment, report, continuous monitoring).
ISO/IEC 22989:2022 (AI concepts and terminology) ⁸	It establishes a common vocabulary of AI (e.g. definitions of AI systems, lifecycle, bias, etc.). It gives all parties a common knowledge base, a prerequisite of transparency and accountability in AI projects. It also gives a conceptual baseline cited by others (e.g. lifecycle in 23894). By standardizing terminology, it prevents confusion and fosters adherence (e.g. adopted by NIST and OECD in definitions).	Referenced throughout Section 4 as baseline terminology (e.g., lifecycle phases, bias definition, model generalisation).
ISO/IEC TR 24027:2021 (Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision making) ⁹	It focuses on mitigation of bias and fairness all along the AI lifecycle. It provides techniques to detect, quantify, and reduce bias in datasets and algorithms. It imposes non-discrimination and equity, which is a core trust principle, by guiding AI engineers to use fairness metrics. It complements risk standards by addressing a	Section 4.2.3 (bias identification in datasets); 4.3.6 (bias mitigation during modelling); 4.5.1 (fairness in clinical validation).

⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77608.html>

⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/81118.html>

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77304.html>

⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/74296.html>

⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/77607.html>

	typical AI ethical risk (biased algorithms) through distinctive best practices (e.g., measures of bias, techniques of rebalancing).	
ISO/IEC 42001:2023 (AI - Management System) ¹⁰	It defines a holistic AI governance framework for organizations. It requires setting up policies and procedures covering ethical AI, risk and lifecycle management, and continuous improvement. It focuses on accountability, organizational oversight, and compliance (e.g., compatibility with EU AI Act's quality system clauses).	Section 4.6 (overarching management, governance, accountability).
ISO/IEC 25012:2008 (Data Quality Model) ¹¹	It specifies a high data quality framework with 15 quality characteristics (e.g., accuracy, completeness, consistency, timeliness, security). It supports data governance by mandating training and input data to be of these quality characteristics. It enhances AI reliability and fairness (with good data reducing errors and biases) and privacy/security (with data confidentiality).	Section 4.2.1–4.2.3 (data sanitisation, pseudonymisation, quality checks).
ISO/IEC TS 4213:2022 (Assessment of ML classification performance) ¹²	It standardizes evaluation methods for ML classification performance. It promotes use of consistent metrics (e.g., sensitivity, specificity, precision/recall) and test procedures. It recommends enhancing transparency and accuracy by mandating that AI performance be honestly measured and reported.	Section 4.3.3 (performance benchmarking); 4.5 (external validation).

For the AI-PROGNOSIS project and similar projects, these standards enable an upgrade to the trustworthy AI development process. By following ISO 23894's risk management procedures, by obtaining data quality as per ISO 25012, through constructive inclusiveness of TR 24027's controls for bias, by evaluating ML model performances as per ISO 4213, and potentially certifying the company as per ISO 42001, the project can show adherence to international best practices in ethical, transparent, and reliable AI. The challenge is the ability to employ them in a holistic and efficient manner. By doing so, not only technical compliance is strengthened, but more importantly stakeholder trust is fostered.

3.7 FUTURE-AI: International consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable AI in healthcare

The recently published FUTURE-AI framework provides guidance for the development and deployment of trustworthy AI tools in healthcare. It is a comprehensive international consensus guideline that aims to ensure that AI systems in healthcare are not only technically sound but also can be deployed in real-world clinical settings (Lekadir et al., 2025). This guideline was established through international consensus over a 24 month period using a modified Delphi approach (Grime & Wright, 2016), and it defines six core guiding principles for trustworthy healthcare AI:

- Fairness – promoting fair development and utilization of AI, non-discrimination, and inclusive participation of underrepresented groups.

¹⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/42001>

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/35736.html>

¹² <https://www.iso.org/standard/79799.html>

- Universality - guaranteeing broad application and transferability of AI systems between institutions, geographies, and populations.
- Traceability – needing clear documentation of datasets, models, and decision-making pipelines to enable auditability and reproducibility.
- Usability – combining human-centred design, intuitive interfaces, and workflow integration to provide clinical relevance and adoption.
- Robustness – requiring resilience against variations in data, adversarial cases, and shift in distributions, while having predictable behaviour in practice settings.
- Explainability – rendering models understandable to a variety of users (clinicians, regulators, patients) both within inherent design and post-hoc interpretation methods.

These principles reinforce and build upon existing standards such as ALTAI, the EU AI Act, and ISO/IEC standards. Indeed, FUTURE-AI operationalizes high-level concepts into clinically relevant guidance that applies both to system deployment and technical development.

The FUTURE-AI principles map directly to the structure of our updated framework:

- Fairness is addressed in Section 4.1.3 (identifying fairness goals and protected attributes) and Section 4.5.1 (ensuring diversity and non-discrimination in clinical validation).
- Universality aligns with Section 4.3.1 (training for generalisation) and Section 4.5.2 (observability and validation across diverse datasets).
- Traceability is embedded in Section 4.6.2 (model and dataset reporting) and Section 5.4.8 (auditability and accountability).
- Usability resonates with Section 4.4 (UX/UI and deployment, clinician-facing explainable AI) and Section 5.3 (user feedback and UI optimisation).
- Robustness corresponds to Section 4.3.2 (adversarial training and regularisation), 4.3.3 (performance benchmarking), and 4.3.5 (uncertainty benchmarking).
- Explainability is directly embedded in Section 4.1.2 (explainability tailored to each user) and Section 4.3.4 (explainable model design).

By integrating the FUTURE-AI guideline in our system, we ensure that our methodology for AI-PROGNOSIS is fully aligned with the new global consensus about trustworthy and deployable clinical AI. This supports the clinical validity, regulatory alignment, and use cases of our models.

4 The AI-PROGNOSIS framework for AI development and evaluation

Building on the concrete ALTAI requirements presented in Section 3 and the general definitions of AI trustworthy dimensions addressed in Section 2, this section establishes the framework (guidelines, methods, and tools) to be adopted by research and development teams to create the AI components of the project, ensuring trustworthiness. The main idea is to put in practice the concepts of HAO, TRS, PDG, TPR, DnDf, SEW, and ACC of the HLEG-AI for each key stage of the AI lifecycle in the project: 1) Design and specification, 2) Data preparation, 3) Development and validation, 4) user experience (UX) / user interface (UI) and deployment, 5) External validation, and 6) Overarching management and workflow. It is worth noting that, based on the suggestion of the HLEG, the ALTAI is intended for flexible use, and organisations can draw on elements relevant to their particular AI system. Therefore, the ALTAI components were reviewed in terms of their relevance to the products AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop and the relevant components are summarised in **Table 11**, associated with

key stages in the development lifecycle of AI models within the project. Compared to D2.2, this updated Section 4 introduces major changes: a dedicated clinician-facing explainability subsection (4.4.7.1), the adoption of LLM-based explanation pathways, the addition of a lifecycle Risk Management System & File (4.6.6). Beyond these structural additions, most sections were also rewritten with a refined that serves as a general guideline.

Table 11 ALTAI requirements and summary of relevant components associated with key stages in the development lifecycle of AI models within AI-PROGNOSIS.

AI system lifecycle	ALTAI requirement	Summary of relevant ALTAI components
Design and specification	HAO	Implementation of protocols avoiding over-reliance by end users. Establishing processes to prevent inadvertent effect of the AI system on human autonomy. Enabling human oversight human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, and human-in-command).
	TRS	Definition of risk metrics and levels. Establishing procedures for monitoring and documenting the system’s accuracy, ensuring clear communication of expected accuracy to end-users or subjects.
	PDG	Consider the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy, the right to physical, mental and/or moral integrity and the right to data protection. Align the AI-system with relevant standards or protocol for data management and governance.
	TPR	Identification of user needs regarding explainability of the AI system’s decision(s).
	DnDF	Utilisation of publicly available technical tools to enhance the understanding of data, model, and performance. Identification of potential biases throughout the AI system’s lifecycle. Definition of group/individual fairness goals and of protected attributes. Establish mechanisms for flagging bias, discrimination, or low performance issues.
	ACC	Enabling and facilitating the AI system’s auditability.
Data preparation	TRS	Ensuring the high quality of the data
	PDG	Application of data privacy mechanisms for data collected, generated or processed over the course of the AI system’s lifecycle
	DnDF	Avoid, correct, and monitor unfair bias
Development and internal validation	TRS	Assessing potential vulnerabilities of the AI system. Implementing robust measures throughout the system’s lifecycle to ensure its robustness and overall security. Ensuring the reproducibility of the developed AI models. Performance benchmarking, including reliability assessment through uncertainty and generalisation evaluation.
	PDG	Model assessment in terms of data leaking, missing data, and membership/attribute inference vulnerabilities.
	TPR	Explanation of the decision by the AI system to its end users (explainability benchmarking).
	DnDF	Assessing and mitigating bias throughout the model development phase.
UX/UI and deployment	HAO	Ensuring end-users or subjects are informed about the AI system’s influence on decisions or outcomes. Establishing mechanisms to detect and address any adverse effects generated by the AI system on end-users or subjects (Adversarial testing in early deployment).

	TRS	Notification of users upon detecting new threats. Evaluation of the dependency of critical system decisions on its stable behaviour.
	PDG	Enabling end-users or subject to have the right to withdraw consent, object, and be forgotten in the AI system.
	TPR	Ensuring that the end-users understand the decision(s) of the AI system.
	DnDF	Assessing the system's user interface for usability by individuals with special needs, disabilities, or those at risk of exclusion is essential.
External validation	TRS	Performance evaluation, including reproducibility and reliability evaluation
	TPR	Evaluation of quality and adequacy of model output explanations by end-users in clinical studies
	DnDF	Diverse participant sample in clinical studies for external validation of performance and user acceptance evaluation.
Overarching management and workflow	TRS	Assessment of the risk of possible malicious use, misuse or inappropriate use of the AI system.
	PDG	Supporting AI governance strategies. Establishing mechanisms to flag issues related to privacy or data protection.
	SEW	Ensure the understanding and assessment of the impacts of the AI system on work, skills, and society at large as part of the general socio-ethical implications assessment.

Within the following subsections, specific components corresponding to each stage of AI development are presented. These components are the AI PROGNOSIS components and are designed to be integrated into the project. They contain actions aimed at building a trustworthy AI system that meets the outlined ALTAI requirements (summarised in **Table 11**) as well as of other pertinent trustworthy AI frameworks, such as the AI Act and the MDR. In the following, methods and steps described are linked to their associated ALTAI requirement(s) using light blue-shaded labels, e.g., **TPR**.

4.1 Design and specification

Certain of the specifications that influence the design for creating a trustworthy AI system must be decided during the early co-creation and user research phase. These design considerations pertain to pillars of trustworthy AI such as human autonomy, explainability, fairness, biases, and equality. They should be embedded into the AI-enabled components as early as possible, when the ecosystem is still malleable, and will serve as a guide to adhere to for the next phases of development.

4.1.1 Embedding personal autonomy and exercising oversight

Trustworthy AI systems must ensure human autonomy and support human decision-making of the end user while being overseen by human agents in an end-to-end manner. In AI-PROGNOSIS these design specifications become a necessity due to the sensitive nature of healthcare. Personal autonomy and system oversight must be embedded into the system's specifications as early as possible.

4.1.2 Explainability tailored to each user

To guarantee transparent AI-enabled components and to ensure a user-centric system, the explanation of each model's output must be tailored to the background knowledge of each

user group. AI-PROGNOSIS has a diverse range of stakeholders and users meaning special attention must be given to the means of tailoring the explainability experience by considering each user's type (person with PD, person at risk of PD, informal caregiver healthcare professional/enabler) individual needs and capabilities.

4.1.3 Identify fairness goals and protected attributes

Fairness heavily depends on the context of each user. The question "Fair to whom?" can lead to contradictory answers. To create a fair AI system, clear goals for what constitutes it fair to groups and individuals must be set. The goals must be explicit and agreed upon by all stakeholders by taking in account the perspective of the users. This requires the participation of a diverse group of people to the fairness goal identification phase. In addition to fairness goals, any protected attributes, such sex and race, must be also identified for avoiding possible biases and unfair AI enabled components.

4.1.4 Equal access to stakeholders

Ensuring equitable access and engagement of all stakeholders to the design process is vital for a high-quality result in co-creation phase. As a result, the principle of equality must be integrated into the specification and design phase.

4.1.4.1 Methods

Research groups that are involved in AI-enabled components should lead their respective specification and design phase. They should then gather essential feedback through dedicated co-creation workshops and primary user research that aims to:

- Evaluate how AI-enabled components impact human decision-making and autonomy **HOA**.
- Identify the end-users' requirements for explainable and interpretable AI components output **HAO / TPR**.
- Verify and, when necessary, direct research groups to maintain a Human-in-Command system design approach **HAO**.

During the evaluation for impact on human decision-making, a discussion topic should be any overreliance to the AI-enabled components by the end-users. In addition, by utilising results of primary user research, a tailored explainable experience to the knowledge base of every user type will be embedded into the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem. Finally, AI-PROGNOSIS will exercise oversight by following a Human-in-Command approach by trying to augment and/or enhance health care enabler/provider capabilities. This design approach should be affirmed and verified during co-creation workshops. Research groups must use the feedback produced by the workshops to stay on track.

A wide range of information sources will be investigated by research groups to set fairness goals and identify the protected attributes that can add bias to AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem. The goals will be based on the feedback from the diverse and inclusive co-creation workshops. During these workshops the protected attributes must be identified based on the EU Fundamental Rights Agency guidelines for non-discrimination (FRA, 2019). In addition, primary user research and their definition of fairness should be considered. Finally, clinicians should provide their invaluable input on the variables that can add bias based on their previous experience **TPR**.

To ensure equal access to stakeholders and users, co-creation groups should involve people with diverse background, such as developers, expert patient groups and clinicians that are experts in their relevant domain. During the workshops, they should be included and empowered in the conversation. Committed to inclusivity, this assemblage should provide to

the research groups their perspective and feedback, fostering collaboration while embracing the contributions of each individual **DnDF**. For fairness goals to reflect reality, these conditions for the co-creation workshop are crucial and mandatory.

4.2 Data preparation

4.2.1 Outlier detection and data sanitisation

Outlier detection may be applied by leveraging statistical methods such as the z-score, which measures the difference in standard deviations of an observation from the mean (a threshold, such as $z=3$, can be used to detect potential outliers) or the interquartile range (IQR), which identifies outliers based on the first and third quartiles. Any observation outside the $1.5 * IQR$ can be considered an outlier. Data cleansing and sanitisation may be implemented by the following:

- Removal of duplicate records
- Removal of noise from data by removing implausible ranges of values
- Removal of records with missing values: For instance, participants who lack data for several key features or have an insufficient number of longitudinal records for clinically significant data are excluded from the analysis. Alternatively, features that are available for only a small subset of participants may be removed from the analysis to preserve the participant pool. The choice between excluding participants or removing features represents a trade-off between maximizing the sample size and retaining the most clinically significant features.
- Imputation of missing values: e.g. using methods such as interpolation, clustering, and/or regression techniques over time for each participant and feature.
- Standardisation of data formats such as dates, times, categories, units of measurements: e.g. Homogenization of time intervals across all participants and cohorts (e.g. Baseline, Month 6, etc.). For categorical features, data ranges are extracted, while for continuous data, normalization may be used using Z score or min – max values.
- Employment of ML sanitisation methods such as Isolation Forests, One-class support vector machine, auto-encoders.

The result of technical robustness of the described processes will be quantified by measuring and comparing one of or a number of the following metrics: model accuracy, L2 distance, F1 score, correlation (r), coefficient of determination (r^2), and significance (p) between models trained on the original and the cleaned versions of the data.

4.2.2 Data pseudonymisation or anonymisation

Data will be pseudonymised in order to preserve the privacy of the participants in the clinical studies. This process ensures that each subject will be represented by a study id, making it hard to be identified and/or mapped to their data. As identity information of all subjects participating in the clinical studies are kept safely by the corresponding hospitals, this procedure ensures that the subjects cannot be identified. A special case is the direct identification of biological data, such as genetic profiles or blood samples, for which special provisions will be made, e.g., sharing of processed data (instead of raw data) and access control by a data access committee to further reduce the risk of participant identification.

4.2.3 Data quality assessment and bias identification

Differential privacy might be employed by leveraging Google's differential privacy libraries¹³. If applied, privacy threshold Epsilon (ϵ) and loss of privacy Delta (δ) parameters will be tuned accordingly to not degrade model predictions while ensuring the privacy of the data.

In house solutions or pre-existing libraries, such as AI Fairness 360¹⁴ or YData¹⁵ may be used to assess data quality and bias, focusing on identification and evaluation of origin, inclusivity, type of information and appropriateness, missing data, time frame and geographical coverage, as per the EU Fundamental Rights Agency. If applicable, bias mitigation algorithms may be employed, such as optimised pre-processing (Calmon et al., 2017). If needed, bias will be measured by employing metrics, such as the disparate impact (Feldman et al., 2015) and the equal opportunity (Hardt et al., 2016). As an example, significant differences are evident between different cohorts (e.g., PPMI vs. PDBP), when clustering subjects based on their disease progression. These analyses reveal marked differences in progression rates. For instance, the PDBP cohort includes a higher proportion of participants exhibiting more rapid disease progression compared to the PPMI cohort.

If necessary, synthetic data may be created to combat severe class imbalances using methods such as (Z. Zhang et al., 2021); (Tucker et al., 2020), that will be evaluated based on fidelity (realism of synthetic samples), diversity (whether the variability of real data is reflected) and authenticity (number of copies of real samples generated) (R. J. Chen et al., 2021). Synthetic data generation, as well as any approach that will transform/generate data, will be adopted after consultation with regulatory bodies in order not to impede regulatory approval of the predictive models in the future.

4.3 Development and internal validation

4.3.1 Training for generalisation

These components aim at achieving a generalised model TRS. One approach to mitigate overfitting and enhance generalisation involves reducing model complexity. For example, adding a bottleneck layer to a neural network can be effective in this regard (Li et al., 2023). Additionally, regularisation techniques (explicit or implicit regularisations) should be applied, such as early stopping (Yao et al., 2007), batch normalisation (Ioffe & Szegedy, 2015), dropout (Srivastava et al., 2014), data augmentation, and weight decay (Krogh & Hertz, 1991). These techniques help improve model generalisation and aim to limit the model's complexity and guide learning toward a manageable hypothesis space.

4.3.2 Adversarial training and regularisation

During the development of the AI models in AI-PROGNOSIS, adversarial training, which is considered as a defensive method against adversarial attacks (Bai et al., 2021), should be taken into consideration **TRS**. One approach begins with identifying potential adverse attacks, then improve the robustness of the model by augmenting the training data with adversarial samples to create a defence against them (Wang et al., 2019). For this purpose, tools should be adopted like Adversarial Robustness Toolbox¹⁶, that contains a large set of adversarial attacks and defences that are relevant to the models that will be developed, and it is not limited to deep learning. Although not updated recently, CleverHans¹⁷ could also be considered to

¹³ OpenMined. *PyDP*. <https://github.com/OpenMined/PyDP>

¹⁴ Trusted-AI. *AIF360*. <https://github.com/Trusted-AI/AIF360>

¹⁵ ydataai. *ydata-quality*. <https://github.com/ydataai/ydata-quality>

¹⁶ Trusted-AI. *adversarial-robustness-toolbox*. <https://github.com/Trusted-AI/adversarial-robustness-toolbox>

¹⁷ Cleverhans-lab. *cleverhans*. <https://github.com/cleverhans-lab/cleverhans>

evaluate/protect models against adversarial threats of evasion, poisoning, extraction, and inference.

4.3.3 Performance benchmarking

In AI-PROGNOSIS we aim to exhaustively monitor and validate the AI models' performance **TRS**. Tools like the TensorFlow Model Analysis TFMA¹⁸ can be used to perform deep analysis of the AI model's performance and for performing model evaluation across different slices of data. Fit-for-purpose performance metrics will be used to assess the quality of AI models with respect to accuracy, calibration, and uncertainty. Depending on the different type of models implemented, different accuracy metrics will be adopted.

- For PD risk predictive modelling, key accuracy metrics for healthcare predictive models will be used, such as the concordance index (C-index), joined by classification metrics (i.a., classification accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, area under the receiver operating characteristics curve (AUC)).
- For PD progression modelling, two different approaches are considered, 1) prediction of progression outcomes and 2) prediction of disease progression scores at certain future time points. In the former case, metrics such as the weighted accuracy, fi scores, and recall will be used to assess performance, while in the latter, measures of error, such as the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), will be employed.
- Performance metrics for the PD medication response predictive model a set of metrics will be reported, including accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1-score, area under the ROC curve (AUROC), as well as calibration metrics such as intercept, slope, and expected calibration error.

For calibration, the calibration intercept and slope should be estimated, complimented, if necessary, by the prediction interval coverage probability for regressors, or the expected calibration error or Brier score for classifiers. For uncertainty, the prediction interval or the prediction confidence score should be estimated.

On top of the aforementioned performance metrics, reliability should be assessed with uncertainty and calibration metrics, as well as performance metrics evaluated on external datasets (out of distribution data and various shifts) and the datasets collected in the validation clinical studies of the project (AI-PRA and AI-PMP studies). This relates to Section 4.5 'External validation'.

4.3.4 Explainable model design

This component highlights one of the main dimensions of trustworthy AI which is the explainability of the AI system **TPR**. In the project, we should investigate approaches for the two aspects of ML explainability that are mentioned in Section 2.1.3, i.e., testing of inherently explainable models and rendering black box approaches interpretable through both local (explanation of individual outputs for end-users) and global (general model behaviour explanation for regulators and healthcare enablers) explanations. Other approaches can be employed (depending on the model) that combine both aspects in developing and embedding explainable linear models and prototype selection to deep learning models (Li et al., 2023). For this purpose, several actively maintained explainability tools will be explored, such as:

¹⁸ Tensorflow. https://github.com/tensorflow/tfx/blob/master/docs/tutorials/model_analysis/tfma_basic.ipynb

- (1) SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations)¹⁹ that provides a unified measure of feature importance, allowing the understanding of how individual features contribute to model prediction;
- (2) LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations)²⁰ that helps explain the predictions of black-box models by generating locally faithful explanations; and
- (3) Captum²¹ that can be used if deep learning models will be used, including transformer-based models.

Furthermore, a variety of studies have used qualitative metrics to evaluate explainability with human participation. Representative approaches include the subjective human evaluation. The methods of evaluation include interviews, self-reports, questionnaires, and case studies that measure, e.g., user satisfaction, mental models, and trust (Hoffman et al., 2018). The goal in this context is to explore how key stakeholders perceive and comprehend model explanations in decision-making processes. In the AI-PROGNOSIS case, this is foreseen as part of the clinical studies (see Section 4.5.3 'End-user assessment of model output explanations in clinical studies').

4.3.5 Uncertainty benchmarking

This component focuses on addressing uncertainty during the development of ML models **TRS**. A fail-safe system to be implemented to handle the ML model faults by means of recognising predictions that have low confidence score and should not be trusted and that should activate a healing procedure bringing the model to a safe state.

There are two main types of uncertainty (Hüllermeier & Waegeman, 2021), i.e., reducible epistemic uncertainty that arises from the lack of knowledge about the perfect model (usually due to noisy and/or lack of enough training data) and irreducible aleatoric uncertainty, caused by the inherent randomness in the data generation process (e.g., label ambiguity). Predictive uncertainty is the aggregate of those two types. Depending on model type and stage of development (new or pre-trained model), uncertainty should be estimated either intrinsically, through models that inherently provide it (either epistemic or both) along with predictions (such as Bayesian approaches), or via extrinsic methods, extracting uncertainty *post-hoc* (such as Meta-Models).

For classification models, uncertainty is expected to be communicated as a confidence score, while for regression models, it will be a prediction interval. In case of re-calibration for uncertainty improvement, the employed calibration metrics to be used for benchmarking depend on model type, i.e., such as the Expected Calibration Error or Brier score (for classifiers) or the Prediction Interval Coverage Probability (for regressors).

Tools such as Uncertainty Quantification 360²² can be used when applicable. It is a toolkit that provides a broad range of capabilities to streamline as well as foster the common practices of quantifying, evaluating, improving, and communicating uncertainty in the AI application development lifecycle. This tool contains a lot of assessments (*post-hoc* and intrinsic/during training) and metrics, and it is not limited to deep learning. It allows to perform a recalibration if the performance is poor. We will also adopt approaches, similar to previous studies (Becker

¹⁹ SHAP. <https://github.com/shap/shap>

²⁰ LIME. <https://github.com/marcotcr/lime>

²¹ Captum. <https://github.com/pytorch/captum>

²² IBM. UQ360. <https://github.com/IBM/UQ360>

et al., 2021), that use the “defer” to human option for handling the use cases with low confidence.

4.3.6 Assessment and mitigation of bias

As for the **DnDF** components of AI-PROGNOSIS, we should integrate bias mitigation techniques and incorporate feedback mechanisms to adapt to changing conditions and user needs. We intend to develop an AI system with minimum bias by conducting fair training and avoiding inequalities due to the discriminatory forms caused by biases. Fair training methods will be considered:

- (1) At the level of modifying training data before feeding into the model (Pre-processing Fairness) using implementations like re-sampling (balance representation of different groups), re-weighting (assign higher weights to underrepresented groups), and data augmentation (generate synthetic data to increase representation) (Calmon et al., 2017) (Sun et al., 2022).
- (2) At the level of modifying learning algorithms or objective functions (in-processing training) using implementations like adversarial training, and adversarial debiasing (Wan et al., 2023) (B. H. Zhang et al., 2018).
- (3) At the level of adjusting the model’s predictions after training (post-processing fairness) using implementations like re-ranking (adjust model predictions to ensure equalised odds) and calibration (calibrates model’s predicted probabilities) (Petersen et al., 2021) (Putzel & Lee, 2022).

In this context, and during the development of ML models in the project, actively maintained libraries/tools that can help detect and mitigate unwanted bias in the developed models will be utilised such as the well documented AI Fairness 360, which provides a wide range of metrics, algorithms, and tutorials to help detect and mitigate bias in AI models, and FairML²³, which offers various metrics for evaluating the fairness of ML models, such demographic parity, a fairness metric used to assess whether the positive outcome is distributed equally among different demographic groups.

4.3.7 Selection of production model - performance and privacy risk trade-off

During the development of ML models in the project, if there is a risk that the model, even if accurate, might compromise privacy, leading to concerns about data leaks, re-identification of individuals, employing techniques like differential privacy can help minimise the exposure of sensitive data while still enabling model training or inference. The aim of this is to balance the trade-offs between performance and privacy risks.

4.4 UX/UI and deployment

4.4.1 User feedback

User feedback about the outputs of an AI model can help discover biases and incorrect predictions and understand the usefulness and adoption of an AI application. In order to assure that the feedback received is effective, we must carefully decide which users should provide it, whether external domain experts or the end users.

Another factor that should be considered is the type of user feedback that should be collected. We should implement both explicit and implicit feedback mechanisms. Explicit feedback is the one that users intentionally provide and should be systematically gathered. It can be quantitative, where users must answer a simple question of correct/incorrect or provide ratings

²³ FairML. <https://github.com/adebayoj/fairml>

on a scale out of 5, or qualitative where users should be given opportunities to provide written feedback freely, mostly through text boxes. We should prioritize explicit feedback if the aim is increasing model performance. On the other hand, implicit user feedback refers to unintentional provided data based mostly on users' behavioural patterns and should be monitored to understand actual usage patterns (Hodgson, 2023).

We must collect general user feedback on the AI model's performance and should provide users with clear options to verify, dispute, and correct the AI outputs **HAO**.

4.4.2 Adversarial testing

The deployment framework must integrate seamlessly with existing MLOps practices and should provide automated testing protocols, performance benchmarking, and continuous monitoring capabilities that scale with the project's needs. We must establish clearly defined threat models that specify adversarial capabilities and objectives, ensuring that testing scenarios remain relevant to current attack methodologies while maintaining development efficiency (Biggio & Roli, 2018; Akhtar & Mian, 2018). Ultimately, we should implement adversarial testing as an integral component of the CI/CD pipeline rather than treating it as an isolated security assessment, and must prioritize proactive identification of vulnerabilities before they can impact end-users. **TRS**.

4.4.3 Disclaimers

A disclaimer is a statement or notice intended to limit the legal liability or responsibility of the person or entity providing the information. It is a way to inform others that the information presented may not be complete, accurate, or applicable in all situations, and that the provider is not assuming full responsibility for any consequences that may arise from relying on the information.

Disclaimers are commonly used in various contexts, such as websites, contracts, product labels, and written materials, to address issues like potential errors, omissions, or the specific conditions under which the information is valid. The goal is to protect the party providing the information from legal claims and to make users or consumers aware of the limitations associated with the provided content.

Within AI-PROGNOSIS, disclaimers across software tools and in dedicated sections should be added to help increase transparency, mitigate risk and reduce liability and misinterpretation by the users. The following disclaimers should be present:

- Disclaimer on the expected model performance **TRS**.
- Disclaimer on AI function and required input of personal data **PDG**.
- Disclaimer regarding unavoidable bias **DnDF**.

4.4.4 Input data validation

Data validation is an important process when conducting research and it is crucial for ensuring the accuracy and completeness of the data. Inconsistent or incomplete data most of the times can be proven of little use. It is best that we construct data so no time and resources are wasted in cleaning and transforming.

There are ways that we can achieve data validity within AI-PROGNOSIS:

Data type, completeness, and structure check: Before utilising the data, we should ensure that the data received have the desired type and structure and there are no missing values. If there are missing values, we should either populate the data or discard it altogether. When data are input directly by users through questionnaires or forms, incomplete submissions must not be saved to maintain data integrity and prevent partial records from affecting model performance.

However, concerning data from sensors (in this case smartwatches), we must implement comprehensive data quality checks that assess temporal consistency and physiological plausibility, as these continuous data streams may contain intermittent gaps or anomalous readings that require sophisticated validation.

Standardised user input: We should ensure that users input data through standardised procedures, mostly through answering multiple choice questions and disabling submission of the input before it is complete. We should avoid fields with free text typing since they are very prone to inconsistencies and whenever users are required to input numerical values, we should ensure that impossible values (e.g., negative age) cannot be entered **TRS**.

4.4.5 Data minimisation

The principle of data minimisation means that we should limit the collection and use of personal data to what is completely necessary to fulfil a specific task and only that. In this spirit, we should implement local data processing where possible, minimizing data transmission to external servers. We must also limit the retention of those data to only the specific amount of time that is required for the completion of that task²⁴ **PDG**.

4.4.6 Right to be forgotten

The right to be forgotten, also known as the right to erasure, allows individuals to request the deletion of their personal data when it is no longer necessary for the purpose for which it was collected, or when they withdraw their consent. We, as data controllers, are obligated to respond to erasure requests within a reasonable timeframe and to communicate the decision to the data subject **PDG**.

4.4.7 Explanation of models and their outputs

Explainability in healthcare AI is of utmost importance, as it is essential for stakeholders to build trust in and accept the technology. This need can be separated into two key dimensions: it is critical to explain not only how a model reached its conclusion but also what the most important features and predictors are. This is especially vital in clinical decision support systems, where such explanations allow clinicians to detect erroneous predictions and false positives (Amann et al., 2020).

Providing explanations is especially challenging in cases where the system behaves as a black-box. A 'black-box' in terms of explainable AI (XAI) is a model that operates as an opaque system, the inner processes of which are inaccessible and/or uninterpretable (Hassija et al., 2024). By utilising established model-agnostic methods for post-hoc explainability, such as SHAP and LIME, engineers can gain insight into the model's inner processes by examining its behaviour in response to given inputs. However, the challenge lies in effectively communicating these insights in an interdisciplinary manner, as end-users require explanations tailored to their specific expertise and understanding.

From a UI/UX perspective, conventional data visualisation is not sufficient for presenting the intricate data produced by XAI algorithms. Therefore, solutions should be investigated to create visual reports along with statistics and text in accessible language which can then be seamlessly integrated into mobile or web applications. Explanations of the model's underlying mechanisms and architecture should also be provided in language appropriate to the user's background and expertise. In addition, the ability of Large Language Models (LLMs) to generate natural text could be leveraged to provide textual explanations of the decision process in natural language translating technical terms to concepts that users can readily understand.

²⁴ https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/data-protection/glossary/d_en

4.4.7.1 Clinician-facing explainable AI

As part of the user interface and deployment layer, special consideration must be given to the interpretability of AI outputs by clinical end-users. In AI-PROGNOSIS, this becomes especially important for wearable-derived predictions, which clinicians must understand, question, and act upon. In this section, related work and research in clinician-facing explainable AI systems for wearables are covered in terms of findings and gaps in recent literature

Explainability is being recognized as a requirement for wearable-based clinical AI. There have been promising proofs of concept of explainable AI improving model transparency in PD monitoring, in predicting cardiac risk, and in diabetes management. These applications show that if explanations of models are made transparent to clinicians in a clear format, such as through SHAP graphs, highlight visualizations, or rule-based alerting, clinicians can better interpret AI predictions and thus have greater trust in it. The field is still maturing, and more research is still needed in usability under real-world conditions, minimizing cognitive burden, and making explanations of AI consistent with decision-making in clinical practice. Experts suggest greater involvement of clinicians in designing explainable AI systems, further user testing (to include measurement of interpretation speed, accuracy, and cognitive burden), and construction of interactive explanations.

Table 12 is an outline of key studies (2018–2025) involving explainable ML models with wearable-derived features in healthcare. The table below summarises each study in terms of their source of data, AI model, explainable AI approach, and presentation of explanations to clinicians.

Table 12 Clinician-facing explainable AI tools

Study (Year)	Wearable data & feature extraction	Explainable AI Method	Clinician interface
(Wu et al., 2024)	Multi-site motion sensors measuring gait and limb movement. Features (e.g., shank range-of-motion) extracted via statistical analysis	SHAP and LIME for post hoc feature importance	Visual feature-importance plots identifying top motor features. (No dedicated UI; explanations presented in study figures.)
(Gouverneur et al., 2023)	Electrodermal Activity (EDA) from wearable sensors during induced pain. Both raw time-series and hand-crafted features (e.g., statistical features) were extracted	Recursive Feature Elimination (RF feature importance) and Grad-CAM (Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping) for CNNs	Graphical explanations: feature importance rankings from RF, and heatmaps over EDA signal segments via Grad-CAM highlighting important regions
(Mankodiya et al., 2022)	Inertial sensors (accelerometers/gyroscopes) at up to 5 body location. Used the UMAFall public dataset; features are time-series from each sensor axis.	LIME (Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations) applied to time-series predictions	Explanations available through a prototype system: LIME highlights the contribution of sensor features at each timestep to the fall/not-fall decision (e.g., which sensor axis triggered the alert).
(Shah et al., 2025)	Physiological & lifestyle data (systolic/diastolic BP, BMI, cholesterol-glucose ratio, plus lifestyle factors) from public cohorts. (Wearable-related inputs like physical activity	SHAP values for feature attribution (global and local), plus dimensionality reduction plots (t-	Dashboard-style visualizations: SHAP bar charts showing each risk factor's contribution to an individual's risk, and 2D plots (PCA/t-SNE)

	were indirectly represented as lifestyle parameters.)	SNE, PCA) for insight	illustrating patient clusters by risk profile
(De La Cruz et al., 2024)	Continuous glucose from CGM plus wearable-derived vital and activity data (heart rate, step count, calories burned. Data from 24 type-1 diabetes patients' devices.	No post-hoc explainer needed – model is intrinsically interpretable. The learned rules themselves (e.g., thresholds on HR and glucose) serve as explanations	glUCModel application: a clinician/patient-facing app where the rule-based predictions are displayed in plain language (e.g., “If glucose dropping and heart-rate > X, high risk of hypoglycemia” – derived from the learned rules). The app provides alerts with rationale.
(Prendin et al., 2023)	Continuous glucose monitor (CGM) data, insulin dosing records, and meal/carbohydrate info (worn insulin pumps/monitors) from type-1 diabetes patients.	SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) applied to each model's predictions to interpret feature influences	Explanations were analysed via SHAP value plots for each input feature (insulin, carbs, previous glucose) to see if the model's behaviour was physiologically sound. In a clinician-facing DSS, this could be shown as a rationale for recommended insulin doses (e.g., “recent exercise lowered glucose, model accounted for this”).

In AI-PROGNOSIS, we will implement an approach that leverages LLMs to translate feature importance values from SHAP and LIME into clear, contextual explanations for clinicians. These LLMs will take the technical XAI outputs as input and generate natural language explanations that clinicians can readily understand without requiring expertise in data science. This textual interpretation will be presented alongside dedicated graphs and visualizations to provide a comprehensive understanding of the model's decision-making process. The tailored explanations will be presented along with graphs, statistics and elements for communicating uncertainty, with the aim of ensuring that the information provided is accessible and understandable to each user group. Furthermore, an explanation of the model's overall functioning will be provided within the application in appropriate language that matches the end-user's level of technical understanding. This approach will enhance the overall user experience and will foster trust and transparency. **TPR**.

4.4.8 Educational content on AI

We must create and provide tailored educational content that helps users better understand how the underlying AI technology works behind the scenes, making it more accessible and less intimidating for users who may not have a technical background.

Mental models, as defined by Google's People + AI Research team, represent users' internal understanding of how a system works, including their expectations about its capabilities, limitations, and behaviour patterns²⁵. These cognitive frameworks help users predict system responses, understand when and why the AI might fail, and develop appropriate trust calibration based on the system's actual performance rather than misconceptions or unrealistic expectations. One of the primary objectives of the educational content that will be

²⁵ Mental models: <https://pair.withgoogle.com/chapter/mental-models/>

available through the mAI-Health and mAI-Care apps will be to create such mental models, maintaining realistic expectations about their diagnostic and predictive capabilities. **TPR**.

4.4.9 UI/UX best practices and performance optimisation

User interface (UI) and user experience (UX) best practices are guidelines and principles that help designers create effective, user-friendly, and aesthetically pleasing digital products. We must adopt such practices as they are crucial in user adherence and the overall success of the product, including collection of input data and communication of AI outputs and related disclaimers. Those include:

- Implement multi-language support with culturally appropriate health terminology.
- Format consistency throughout the app so users do not get confused.
- Hierarchy and readability of the components so users can easily be guided through the content, by prioritising important elements using visual cues like font size, colour and spacing.
- Accessibility factors such as colour contrast and text size to make the app easier to use by people with disabilities.
- Performance optimisation by reducing loading times and resource usage. We can achieve this by limiting data transmissions to the minimum and closing any unnecessary connections.

The relevant UI/UX principles (including those for accessibility) can be adopted as the design basis, i.e., Google's Material Design²⁶. Those principles are being validated during co-creation sessions and user test feedback **DnDF**.

4.5 External validation

4.5.1 Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness in clinical studies

While Section 4.2 (Data Preparation) identifies bias mitigation at the dataset level, external validation specifically evaluates if bias mitigation strategies remain effective on unseen, independent datasets derived from the clinical studies (AI-PRA and AI-PMP). Thus, efforts should be made to include a diverse participant sample in the AI-PRA and AI-PMP clinical studies for external validation of performance and user acceptance evaluation of the AI tools. In this vein, the datasets derived from clinical studies must exhibit diversity and representativeness of the population, with careful consideration given to the selection of features. Demographic elements, such as age and gender, will be subject to examination, given the variation in symptoms of PD among individuals of different demographics. Additionally, the various stages of PD can serve as another criterion for the diversity of the datasets. **DnDF**.

4.5.2 Observability for robust clinical data validation

Observability is a critical aspect of ML, especially when it comes to external validation using clinical data. It involves the capability to gain a comprehensive understanding of a model's performance through monitoring and alerting. This goes beyond simple debugging, as it plays a key role in providing insights into metrics that signal potential issues within a model operating in a real-world clinical setting.

In the context of clinical data, observability becomes crucial for detecting anomalies such as data drifts and concept drifts. Data drifting occurs when there is a shift in the statistical properties of input data, causing the model to make inferences from values that deviate from the original training datasets. Meanwhile, concept drifting involves a change in the relationship

²⁶ Google Material Design. <https://material.io/design>

between features and the dependent variable over time. Both phenomena can result in model degradation and compromise the reliability of ML pipelines within clinical applications.

To address these challenges in AI-PROGNOSIS, different tools and services can be utilised. One such tool is Evidently AI²⁷, which employs statistical algorithms to detect anomalies, providing a valuable means of identifying deviations in clinical data. It allows maintaining constant logging of model predictions, and an alert system needs to be in place to facilitate an efficient process of model re-evaluation and retraining (Shankar & Parameswaran, 2022). This emphasis on observability ensures the ongoing reliability and accuracy of ML models in the dynamic change of clinical data **TRS**.

4.5.3 End-user assessment of model output explanations in clinical studies

As already mentioned in Section 4.4, different XAI outputs can be generated for the same model depending on the end user, whether it is a patient a healthcare professional, or healthcare enabler and policy maker. In the prospective AI-PRA and AI-PMP clinical studies for external validation of performance and user acceptance evaluation of the AI tools, evaluation of quality and adequacy of AI model output explanations and of the associated UI elements will be requested by participants, including healthcare professionals. In addition to traditional XAI methods (e.g., SHAP, LIME, Captum), and as mentioned in Section 4.4.7, in AI-PROGNOSIS we are also adopting LLM-based approaches to generate natural-language explanations of AI predictions. **TRS**.

4.6 Overarching management and workflow

The elements that are described in this section are related to the general procedures needed to constitute a system trustworthy that are not strictly related to any lifecycle phase of the system but more to management of by-products and processes of AI-PROGNOSIS. Methods that should be used are described under each section and they are accompanied by their respective ALTAI requirements.

4.6.1 Model operations

Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) is an emerging paradigm that combines DevOps with ML. It formulates a set of principles and best practices in ML development, monitoring, and deployment to be used in production. By following a set of procedures and concepts, such as having reproducible models, versioning (models, data and code), continuous training/evaluation and logging, ML workflow can be optimised. Some key aspects of MLOps that are related to trustworthy AI are:

- Model performance monitoring
- Output logging
- Data, model and code versioning
- MLOps platform selection to ensure security

The establishment of a model performance monitoring mechanism during the development lifecycle can enable model tracking and expedite the generation of model performance reports. By keeping a log-record of model inferences (output logging), model performance can be analysed, and can result in AI enabled components that can be audited. Moreover, reproducible ML models are crucial for a trustworthy AI system as they can uphold the verification and validity of the results and behaviour, help error detection, and facilitate identification and addressing of biases. For these key aspects to be accomplished, it is imperative to utilise a secure and robust platform to assure data integrity and confidentiality.

²⁷ Evidently AI. <https://www.evidentlyai.com/>

4.6.1.1 Methods

The MLFlow platform²⁸ should be utilised to facilitate MLOps procedures. It is a highly regarded open-source platform that, among other features, offers model performance monitoring, logging, data and model versioning. The MLFlow project further has a system of vulnerability reporting to safeguard their application programming interface (API) or notify users of alternative means to secure their application.

Model performance logging during validation could be performed by utilising MLFlow logging. Cases of underperformance will be flagged and scrutinised by research groups **TRS**.

All the models produced in the AI-PROGNOSIS project should reside in a model registry or a similar setup along with information regarding their validation metrics. This type of model versioning will ensure reproducibility but also facilitate tracking the development process by keeping previous iterations of models with their respective validation metrics **TPR / ACC**.

Output logging must be performed in all models used in the production environment **TRS**.

Git version control system must be used to track all code produced in AI-PROGNOSIS project **TPR / ACC**.

4.6.2 Model and dataset reporting

For an ML model to be considered transparent, it is necessary to provide a detailed reporting during its lifecycle. In addition, reports that can be accessed by end users and third parties are elevating the accountability of the system. The essential reports pertain to:

- Datasets used
- Model development workflow
- Model validation

4.6.2.1 Methods

Data used for training AI-PROGNOSIS ML models will be sourced mostly from restricted datasets. In contrast, data used for validating AI-PROGNOSIS ML models will be products of the project. In absence of standardised means of documentation on datasets, dataset reports and documentation should be produced based on “datasheets for datasets” (Gebru et al., 2021) were possible with emphasis in datasets used in validation **TPR / ACC**.

Two of the most general guidelines that provide end-to-end checklists, from conception to validation of the model, are the TRIPOD-AI (Collins et al., 2024), along with its recent extension for LLMs (Gallifant et al., 2025), and the Minimum Information about Clinical Artificial Intelligence Modeling (MI-CLAIM) (Norgeot et al., 2020). TRIPOD-AI is an updated version of TRIPOD 2015 (Moons et al., 2015) that is tailored for reporting AI-driven predictive model studies in healthcare. MI-CLAIM is a checklist designed to improve the transparent reporting of AI algorithms in medicine by defining a minimum set of requirements that need to be fulfilled to ensure transparent and adequate reporting. For the AI-PROGNOSIS project, the TRIPOD-AI checklist is considered more appropriate due to its more recent release and its more comprehensive nature compared to MI-CLAIM. Thus, reports for each ML model developed and validated in AI-PROGNOSIS project should be generated based on the TRIPOD-AI checklist^[OBJ], and short summaries should be presented in the format of model cards as published by Google (Mitchell et al., 2019). These model cards²⁹ a standardized way to document model information, intended uses, limitations, and performance characteristics in a concise, accessible format. **TPR / ACC**.

²⁸ MLFlow - <https://mlflow.org/>

²⁹ TRIPOD-AI checklist - <https://www.tripod-statement.org/resources/>

4.6.3 Open models and datasets

Opening datasets and ML model architectures brings several tangible benefits such as:

- Transparency and responsible AI
- Validation and reproducibility
- Research advancement

In order to be aligned with ethical and trustworthy AI development practices, models and datasets should be published and made open. This, fosters trust, transparency and accountability. In addition, open models/validation datasets ensure the reproducibility of the results. Finally, innovation can be fostered as researchers with diverse background can use the results for collective advancement and knowledge. However, it is imperative to safeguard the system and ensure security, privacy, protection of intellectual property rights (IPR), and mitigate potential risks of future exploitation. This means that a careful balance between transparency and securing sensitive components of the system should be maintained.

4.6.3.1 Methods

All datasets produced by AI-PROGNOSIS project will be pseudonymised and made freely available after an embargo period. The Zenodo³⁰ open science repository will be used. As a result, data archiving and sharing will conform to the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) principles³¹ **TPR**.

ML models that are not protected by intellectual property rights must be made available only after ensuring that sensitive data cannot be extracted by model manipulation **TPR / ACC**.

4.6.4 Security and GDPR compliance

All the components of the system must be fully compliant with the relevant regulations and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This includes all project processes and products including AI components and associated tools. Furthermore, key components of the system must be scrutinised for security.

4.6.4.1 Methods

AI-PROGNOSIS has a dedicated data management team that supervise the data collection, exchange, storing and processing to be compliant with the GDPR. They must ensure full compliance of all processes and tools with the regulatory framework, including the AI components and associated tools **PDG**.

Ethics and data protection impact assessment (deliverables D1.3 'Ethics and data protection impact assessment report (initial)' and D1.4 'Ethics and data protection impact assessment report (midterm)') will be conducted at strategic time points in the project (month 7 and month 23), before main research and development, as well as data collection phases. Moreover, a data management plan must be produced and maintained through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Argos service³² to facilitate the compliance of data management and curation with GDPR **PDG**.

Third party datasets that will be accessed by AI-PROGNOSIS consortium members must be handled according to their respective license. Moreover, for the exchange of data, partners must sign data transfer and data use agreements **PDG**.

A privacy-by-design approach must be used while designing the project's digital ecosystem. By being proactive, data de-identification (removal all personal information) must be

³⁰ Zenodo - <https://zenodo.org/>

³¹ FAIR principles - <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

³² EOSC Argos - <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/>

performed (PDG). In addition, data must be disclosed only to partners that must process them **PDG**. Given that the concept of privacy is intertwined with system security, a security assessment of the components of the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem must be performed by the AI-PROGNOSIS consortium **TRS / PDG**. In addition, industry security best practices must be followed such as:

- hosting the Cloud infrastructure with a reputable provider
- having firewalls to protect the Cloud infrastructure
- use of VPN to access hosted resources
- use of Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) / Transport Layer Security (TLS) / Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPs) for encrypted communication where applicable
- use of Identity and Access Management agents where applicable

4.6.5 Sustainability and societal impact

Trustworthy AI systems must be evaluated for their sustainability and their environmental footprint. ML models may need significant computational resources for training, validation, deployment and maintenance. In addition, AI tools, such as those AI-PROGNOSIS is developing, could have socio-ethical implications, impacting work, skills, and society at large, as they are linked to healthcare and involve human-computer interaction.

4.6.5.1 Methods

To reduce the environmental impact of the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem, including its AI operations, the project has selected the Hetzner Cloud provider that is taking measures to protect the environment and has adopted sustainable practices to power its data centres³³. **SEW**.

A report on socio-ethical implications of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools is included this deliverable (Section 2.2) **SEW**.

4.6.6 Risk management system and file

To develop safe and trustworthy AI-enabled medical tools, risk management cannot be treated as a “one-off” exercise. Instead, it should be an ongoing, structured process that runs across the entire lifecycle of the system—from early design, through deployment, and into post-market monitoring.

The EU AI Act (Art. 9) requires that a risk management system to be established, implemented, documented and maintained in relation to high-risk AI systems. In medical contexts, ISO 14971 (2019)³⁴ already provides a widely adopted to assist manufacturers of medical devices to identify the hazards associated with the medical device, to estimate and evaluate the associated risks, to control these risks, and to monitor the effectiveness of the controls and AAMI CR34971 (2019) extends for those performing risk management for AI or ML. As mentioned in Section 3.6, FDA guidance on TPLC emphasizes the same principle: risks must be anticipated, documented, monitored, and updated continuously.

To meet these requirements, in AI-PROGNOSIS, we should commit to maintaining a risk management system consisting of three living documents:

1. Risk management plan
 - Define scope, intended use, and risk acceptance criteria.
 - Assign roles and responsibilities.
 - Plan how adaptive models will be monitored, re-trained, or rolled back.

³³ Hetzner Environmental Protection - <https://www.hetzner.com/unternehmen/umweltschutz>

³⁴ <https://www.iso.org/standard/72704.html>

2. Risk assessment

- Identify hazards: e.g., biased datasets, adversarial attacks, automation bias, privacy breaches, model drift, poor UI design.
- Estimate and evaluate risks: consider both technical and human factors (e.g., how a clinician might misinterpret an output).
- Apply controls: fairness checks, uncertainty estimation, subgroup analysis, adversarial testing, and usability reviews.
- Verify effectiveness: test whether risk controls actually reduce the risks they target.

3. Risk Report

- Document residual risks and explain why they are acceptable given the benefits.
- Provide evidence that controls are working.
- Maintain traceability between identified risks, controls, and outcomes.

In the context of our framework, the above points can be implemented throughout different components:

- During design (Section 4.1): we should anticipate risks linked to autonomy, fairness, explainability, and protected attributes.
- During data preparation (Section 4.2): we should check for data quality, representativeness, and hidden biases.
- During development (Section 4.3): we must perform adversarial testing, uncertainty benchmarking, and subgroup validation.
- During deployment (Section 4.4): we will ensure transparent user interfaces, disclaimers, and model cards that explain limitations.
- During external validation (Section 4.5): we should test across diverse populations, looking for disparities in outcomes.
- During monitoring (Section 4.6): we will keep logs, update the risk management file, and respond quickly to new risks, security threats, or performance drift.

This component will guarantee compliance with EU AI Act and MDR requirements and that clinicians and patients can have more confidence that the system is safe, fair, and reliable.

5 Technical and compliance reporting

5.1 Purpose and scope

This section presents an overview of how the AI-PROGNOSIS partners are implementing Trustworthy AI principles during technical development and deployment phases. It summarizes the responses to compliance questionnaires filled in by the application developers and model developers. These reports cover implementation status and planned actions for improvements on the different trustworthy AI dimensions. Details are provided in the associated WP3 and WP5 deliverables.

5.2 Methodology

Two tailored compliance reporting forms were used:

- UX/UI & Deployment: This report focused on user feedback mechanisms, explainability in the interface, adversarial testing, data minimization, user rights, and educational content. Other aspects such as data security, MLOps practices (e.g., model versioning, logging, monitoring) will be detailed in deliverables D4.4 'The AI-

PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (MVP)' / D4.5 'The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (refined MVP)'.

- Model Development: This report focused on data quality, bias mitigation, explainability, performance validation, robustness, security, and socio-ethical impacts.

It is worth noting that the socio-ethical impacts were Initially included under model development, these have been separated in D2.6 (in Section 5.5) to reflect that socio-ethical considerations are relevant to the entire AI tool and lifecycle. Partners were asked to document what has been implemented so far, and what are the planned next steps for each component of trustworthy AI. The full reporting forms are provided in Appendix I.

5.3 UX/UI and deployment

5.3.1 User feedback

The option for users to provide feedback on the AI models outputs through the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem apps has not yet been implemented. However, future mechanisms for collecting feedback are planned and will be designed based on the specific needs and capabilities of the AI model developer, and these will be described in detail in deliverable D4.5. To improve model performance or application usability —whether through explicit feedback (e.g., forms or ratings) or implicit signals (e.g., usage patterns or corrections)—will depend on how the feedback can be most effectively used to improve model performance and user experience.

5.3.2 Adversarial testing

Adversarial testing is included in the model developers' future evaluation plans and it will be explicitly described in D4.5. This testing is expected to be integrated in later stages of development, with an emphasis on identifying potential vulnerabilities, assessing resistance to input manipulation, and supporting robustness in clinical or other safety-critical contexts.

5.3.3 Input data validation

In all apps, users proceed to data input primarily through multiple-choice questions or by entering numerical values. These inputs are validated in real time to ensure correctness—for example, age cannot be negative, and height must fall within a predefined range. Free-text input is required only in rare cases, and such responses are reviewed manually by a human evaluator.

Comprehensive data quality checks for smartwatch data, keyboard data and active test data will be implemented to ensure completeness, accuracy and reliability of all data streams feeding into the production system. These checks will include validation of sensor data integrity, detection of flat segments indicating potential sensor malfunctions, identification of unrealistic amplitude values and assessment of excessive fluctuations that may indicate data corruption. Details of these checks will be reported in D4.4/D4.5.

Furthermore, a script in the comprehensive motor function assessment is used to perform real-time verification of participant presence and positioning through landmark detection, which is performed every few frames to ensure key body points remain within the camera's field of view. Details of these checks will be reported in D4.4.

5.3.4 Data minimisation

Only the data essential for the system's operation is collected. Users of the mobile applications are requested to provide only data necessary for smartwatch pairing and core application functionalities, with only the minimum required information being saved. For other data sources beyond user-provided information, the same principle applies—only data critical to system functionality is collected and retained. One example is that in the comprehensive

motor function assessment test (see D3.1 ‘First report on digital biomarkers for PD’ and D4.2 ‘The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem (Alpha version)’), an active test employing camera-based body tracking to assess balance, posture and gait, the MediaPipe library³⁵ is used to analyse video directly on the user’s device. Instead of uploading the entire video to the Cloud-based back-end, the system extracts skeletal landmarks locally, preserving privacy and reducing unnecessary data transmission.

5.3.5 Right to be forgotten

Users will have the right to request the deletion of all their data (“right to be forgotten”). Depending on how registration occurs in the MVP—whether directly by the user through the apps or through a healthcare professional—this request can be made through the appropriate channel, and all associated data will be permanently removed from the system.

During the clinical studies, users have the right to withdraw from participation at any time and request the removal of their data from the system. However, it is important to acknowledge that their data may have already been used in the training of AI models and cannot be retroactively removed from those models.

Once a data deletion request is submitted and verified, all associated user data is removed from the system within 60 days.

5.3.6 Explanation of models and their outputs

Explainability components have not been directly integrated into the UI or HCP reports at this stage. Explainability data will be provided by the AI model developers, who are responsible for determining the appropriate methods—such as SHAP, LIME, or custom approaches—based on their models’ architecture and intended use. To ensure these explanations are meaningful to different stakeholders, we are also adopting LLM-based methods to communicate feature explanations in clear, natural language.

Decisions and uncertainty from the models will be communicated to end-users through a combination of visual reports and textual summaries (including LLM-generated explanations). The specific presentation format will depend on the complexity of the output and the needs of the target audience, with an emphasis on clarity, transparency, and usability—especially in clinical or decision-support contexts.

The practical implementation of these explainability strategies will be demonstrated in deliverable D4.4/D4.5, which will showcase how model outputs are reported and explained to users. As LLM-based explanations are still in early development, we plan to address key challenges explicitly: (i) preserving fidelity between the underlying SHAP/LIME outputs and the generated text (the raw SHAP values will also be displayed alongside the textual explanation); (ii) reducing the “black box” effect by adding disclaimers that the textual explanation is AI-generated; and (iii) involving clinicians in validating and rating the adequacy of explanations as part of the evaluation of the mAI-Insights app.

5.3.7 Educational Content on AI

Educational content will be included to help users understand how the AI system works. This material will be produced under Task 6.3 ‘PD educational content development’, in collaboration with technical partners, and will be tailored for the mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications. The practical integration of this educational content into the apps will be showcased in deliverable D4.4/D4.5.

³⁵ MediaPipe Pose Landmarker - https://ai.google.dev/edge/mediapipe/solutions/vision/pose_landmarker

5.3.8 UI/UX best practices and performance optimisation

Our apps incorporate several key principles of Google's Material Design, such as the use of reusable UI components like buttons, cards, dialogs, and navigation drawers. These components follow established design patterns that support common interactions and layouts, ensuring the interface is intuitive and familiar to users. Material Design also emphasizes clear component states and behaviours, helping users understand how to interact with the app effortlessly.

By focusing on contrast and accessibility, the design ensures that content is easy to read and usable by everyone. The thoughtful use of colour, imagery, and typography establishes a strong visual hierarchy, making the experience both attractive and meaningful. Additionally, the application of layers and shadows creates a sense of depth, giving UI elements a tangible feel and aiding users in navigating the interface naturally.

We have carefully considered accessibility features in line with Material Design principles. By emphasizing strong colour contrast, we ensure that text and interactive elements are easily distinguishable for users with visual impairments. We also follow guidelines for scalable font sizes to maintain readability across different devices and user preferences. These accessibility measures, combined with clear component states and intuitive interactions, help make our app usable and welcoming to a diverse range of users.

To ensure performance optimization, we have focused heavily on reducing the number of API calls and minimizing the amount of data transmitted. By carefully batching requests and fetching only the necessary data, we cut down on redundant network traffic and lower loading times.

The mobile application's UI/UX has been thoroughly validated and continuously refined through collaborative co-creation sessions with a dedicated patient panel. Additionally, ongoing feedback is actively gathered from users participating in clinical studies, ensuring that improvements are informed by real-world experiences. This continuous, iterative feedback loop allows us to consistently enhance the user experience, keeping it aligned with patient needs and expectations.

5.4 Model development

This reporting is based on the implementation activities of model developers within WP3, which focuses on predictive modelling and digital biomarker development for PD. The project is developing several key AI models:

- Models encompassed in measurement pipelines of digital biomarkers to track motor and cognitive function in daily life using wearable and smartphone data.
- Genetic profiling models to identify SNPs associated with PD risk, progression, and treatment response.
- PD risk assessment models that estimate a risk score of having PD.
- PD progression prediction models that forecast clinical trajectories, especially motor decline, based on harmonised multi-source datasets.
- Medication response models that predict individual patient responses to treatment, focusing on the appearance of side-effects.

These artefacts form the basis for assessing compliance with the trustworthy AI framework, and detailed evidence of their implementation will be reported in D3.4 'Final report on predictive modelling for PD'.

5.4.1 Data quality and bias mitigation

All partners implemented data quality assessment processes tailored to their respective data modalities. **Table 13** summarises the approaches adopted for the different models. Detailed evidence, results, and future plans will be provided in D3.4.

Table 13 Summary of data quality assessment practices implemented for different AI-PROGNOSIS models

Data quality assessment	
Digital biomarkers	Statistical analyses—including distribution and missingness plots—to assess data from AMP-PD and PPMI, and adopted upsampling and stratification strategies during training to address class imbalance.
Genetic analysis	Rigorous quality control on genetic datasets, excluding SNPs and samples that failed standard thresholds (e.g., call rate <95%, HWE $p < 10^{-5}$, MAF <1%) in line with best practices in genetic association studies.
PD risk assessment model	Extensive exploratory data analysis (EDA) and developed a custom validation tool to ensure schema compliance for clinical data, in addition to preprocessing accelerometer and keystroke data to remove noise and ensure continuity.
PD progression predictive model	Focused on data completeness, applied manual validation and automated quality control, with plans to introduce stricter value constraint enforcement.
Medication response predictive model	Manually inspected datasets for erroneous entries and used fuzzy matching to standardize categorical variables, with plans to address model-driven bias by penalizing overreliance on sensitive features in future retraining cycles.

5.4.2 Outlier detection, data sanitization, privacy, and protected variables

Outlier detection approaches varied across partners based on the nature of their data. **Table 14** summarises these efforts.

Table 14 Summary of outlier detection, data sanitization, privacy, and protected variables practices implemented for different AI-PROGNOSIS models

Outlier detection	
Digital biomarkers	Applied outlier detection during clustering via an autoencoder that flags participants with high reconstruction loss (e.g., MSE above threshold). Participants with insufficient longitudinal records or missing key features were excluded, and further strategies such as isolation forest or manual clinical review are being considered.
Genetic analysis	Included outlier handling implicitly via quality control and covariate adjustments.
PD risk assessment model	Performed exploratory data analysis to examine data distributions and used z-score thresholds and empirical percentiles (e.g., 98th percentile) for keystroke and Verily accelerometer data. In future iterations, z-score-based outlier detection will be extended to feature-level data, with manual review.
PD progression predictive model	Z-score normalization to minimize outlier influence and implemented explicit detection strategies such as IQR and z-score thresholds in future cycles.
Medication response predictive model	Implemented standard statistical outlier detection by removing values beyond three standard deviations from the mean.
Data sanitization	

Digital biomarkers	Employed a comprehensive pipeline combining imputation methods (interpolation, constrained regression) tailored to clinical groups, feature-wise and per participant. Projection and rounding ensured consistency with the original data format.
Genetic analysis	Ensured integrity by storing data on secure institutional servers with access control.
PD risk assessment model	Considered data pseudo-anonymized and stated no sanitization was applicable
PD progression predictive model	Applied k-nearest neighbours imputation after filtering high-missingness features
Medication response predictive model	Relied on previously sanitized datasets without further steps
Privacy	
All models	Confirmed that their datasets were either anonymized or pseudonymized
Protected variables	
All models	Protected variables were identified by clinical experts and plans future fairness evaluations targeting their impact

5.4.3 Model generalization, and robustness across partners

To ensure generalization to unseen data, all modelling partners applied validation strategies and techniques to reduce overfitting. **Table 15** summarises the current implementation practices and future plans for generalisation and robustness. Detailed evidence will be reported in D3.4.

Table 15 Summary of model generalization, and robustness practices implemented for different AI-PROGNOSIS models

Model generalization	
Digital biomarkers	Reported applying methods such as dropout and early stopping during model training to avoid overfitting, in addition to k-fold cross-validation and controlled data augmentation using a sliding window over participants' longitudinal data with different window lengths.
PD risk assessment model	PD risk prediction model will be evaluated on external datasets once access to the UK Biobank is obtained. In case of overfitting in future model iterations, techniques such as resampling during training and generation of synthetic data will be considered.
PD progression predictive model	Validated classification modeling using stratified 5-fold cross-validation and assessed generalizability through separate wearable datasets. Dropout and early stopping were also applied during training.
Medication response predictive model	Trained models through stratified 10-fold cross-validation, ensuring disjoint training and validation subject sets to prevent overfitting to specific subject characteristics. To further promote generalizability, KUL pooled multiple datasets to build a diverse cohort and evaluated model performance across datasets.
Robustness	
Digital biomarkers	Highlighted potential future use of domain adaptation techniques such as Maximum Mean Discrepancy and Optimal Transport to align source and target distributions. More advanced approaches, such as using Generative

	Adversarial Networks to generate feature vectors for target domains, are also being considered to improve generalization across clinical contexts.
PD risk assessment model	Intends to evaluate model robustness—particularly for accelerometer data—using techniques such as noise injection
PD progression predictive model	Do not currently plan to use adversarial training but rely on regularization as a standard practice. In both cases, Random Forest models are used with carefully managed hyperparameters to minimize the performance gap between training and validation and thus maintain robustness.
Medication response predictive model	

5.4.4 Performance benchmarking and evaluation metrics

All modelling partners have defined performance benchmarks, primarily guided by domain-specific literature and validated references. **Table 16** summarises the metrics currently in use and planned for further validation. Detailed benchmarking results will be presented in D3.4.

Table 16 Summary of performance benchmarking practices and evaluation metrics implemented for different AI-PROGNOSIS models

Performance benchmarking and evaluation metrics	
Digital biomarkers	Benchmarks their models against traditional machine learning methods like Random Forests and simpler deep learning architectures such as LSTMs. For classification tasks, they use confusion matrices to compute accuracy, precision, and other standard metrics. In regression scenarios, they report RMSE, MSE, and R ² scores. For slowness of movement digital biomarkers, they plan to use Spearman's correlation, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and pairwise comparisons to assess discrimination across disease severity levels.
PD risk assessment model	For PD risk assessment, evaluation will rely on classification metrics including precision, recall, F1-score, and the C-index derived from ROC analysis, with additional correlation to DaTscan Striatal Binding Ratios (SBR) and UK Biobank confirmed PD cases. The MDS prodromal model will serve as a comparative benchmark.
PD progression predictive model	Set performance benchmarks using existing literature. Their evaluation metrics include Balanced Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score, measured across cross-validation folds to ensure generalizable performance assessment.
Medication response predictive model	Bases performance expectations on literature but acknowledges the challenge of exact replication due to data privacy constraints. To provide a thorough evaluation, they report a broad suite of metrics including accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1-score, AUROC, calibration intercept and slope, and expected calibration error.

5.4.5 Bias assessment and mitigation

Formal bias assessment using fairness metrics has not yet been conducted across the modelling tasks. However, initial qualitative steps have been taken, including visual inspection of model outputs by protected variables, application of up-sampling techniques to address class imbalance, and stratified data splitting to ensure balanced training sets. Once baseline model performance is reliably established, partners plan to assess disparities in performance across demographic or clinical subgroups. If imbalances are detected, mitigation strategies such as sample weighting will be applied. In future iterations, quantitative fairness metrics will be computed to support formal bias evaluation, and dedicated libraries such as Fairlearn or

IBM AI Fairness 360 will be considered as needed to reduce bias without negatively affecting model calibration.

5.4.6 Explainable model design across partners

Explainability strategies vary by model type and partner. **Table 17** summarises the current explainability approaches and planned actions across the different models.

Table 17 Summary of explainable model design practices implemented for different AI-PROGNOSIS models

Explainable model design	
PD risk assessment model	Uses post-hoc explainability methods on more complex models. Applies SHAP for global explanations and both SHAP and LIME for local prediction insights. Complements this with feature importance extracted from trained models.
PD progression predictive model	Applies Random Forests with built-in feature importance. Plans to integrate SHAP in future iterations to provide local and global explanations. For the deep learning architectures, constructs two embedding spaces: one for single-visit feature states and one for longitudinal disease progression. Uses t-SNE and PCA visualizations to reveal clinically meaningful clusters, showing that the model captures relevant disease patterns without biased structuring by protected variables.
Medication response predictive model	Uses Random Forests, which are inherently explainable through feature importance measures (e.g., Gini importance). Plans to develop lightweight decision tree surrogates to mimic Random Forest performance with simple, interpretable rules.

5.4.7 Uncertainty benchmarking across partners

Uncertainty benchmarking has not yet been implemented across the modelling partners, but all have outlined future plans to address it. Planned strategies include analysing which samples the model is most uncertain about and identifying the conditions that lead to such uncertainty. Partners plan to incorporate probabilistic modelling techniques or use methods like Monte Carlo Dropout to quantify prediction reliability. While random forests have been predominantly used so far—and inherently offer uncertainty estimates through measures such as prediction entropy

5.4.8 Model and dataset reporting

To ensure transparency and reproducibility, all model development in AI-PROGNOSIS will adhere to the TRIPOD-AI reporting framework. This approach is used in D3.2 'First report on predictive modelling for PD', which was structured according to TRIPOD-AI. Furthermore, in D3.4 each AI artefact will therefore be documented using the TRIPOD-AI checklist.

5.4.9 Security of models and data

All AI-PROGNOSIS model development activities follow a common baseline of security practices to protect both data and models across their lifecycle. Datasets and trained models are stored on encrypted systems with strict access controls, ensuring that only authorised users with approved credentials can retrieve or modify them. The project infrastructure is further protected through firewalls and standard industry security measures, safeguarding against unauthorised access or tampering.

5.5 Societal and environmental impact

Across the consortium, partners have reflected on the potential socio-ethical implications of their AI models. AUTH emphasized that model design decisions—such as risk score communication and clinician reporting—were informed by multiple co-creation sessions with stakeholders, ensuring alignment with clinical needs and minimizing unintended harm. The system avoids feedback loops to individuals at risk and is intended to support rather than disrupt clinical workflows. CERTH highlighted the potential positive impacts of subtype prediction and progression modelling on personalized treatment, earlier intervention, and reduced clinical workload. However, they also acknowledged risks such as algorithmic bias and possible over-reliance on AI outputs by clinicians. KUL noted that their medication response models aim to support better, more personalized prescriptions, with only minor socio-ethical implications anticipated.

In the case of AING, the progression modelling system is expected to assist clinicians in identifying patients with faster disease progression, thereby supporting earlier interventions or closer monitoring. The model may also help reduce the need for redundant assessments by providing trajectory-based insights. Socio-ethical implications are expected to be minimal, as the tool is designed to augment—not replace—clinical decision-making.

Regarding environmental sustainability, AUTH confirmed that AI-PROGNOSIS uses the eco-friendly Hetzner cloud provider. CERTH plans to reduce GPU usage and track the carbon footprint of future training runs. KUL stated that their models are computationally lightweight, resulting in negligible environmental impact. Similarly, AING operates with modest model sizes and limited compute requirements, ensuring that environmental impact remains minimal.

5.5.1 Auditability and accountability

All partners have implemented or are in the process of establishing mechanisms to ensure auditability and accountability of their AI systems. The table below summarises the socio-ethical reflections for each key predictive model, together with considerations on environmental sustainability. Detailed evidence and evaluation will be further presented in D3.4.

Table 18 Summary of socio-ethical reflections implemented for different AI-PROGNOSIS models

Socio-ethical	
PD risk assessment model	Model design decisions—such as risk score communication and clinician reporting—were informed by multiple co-creation sessions with stakeholders, ensuring alignment with clinical needs and minimizing unintended harm. The system avoids feedback loops to individuals at risk and is intended to support rather than disrupt clinical workflows.
PD progression predictive model	is expected to assist clinicians in identifying patients with faster disease progression, thereby supporting earlier interventions or closer monitoring. The model may also help reduce the need for redundant assessments by providing trajectory-based insights. Socio-ethical implications are expected to be minimal, as the tool is designed to augment—not replace—clinical decision-making
Medication response predictive model	Medication response models aim to support better, more personalized prescriptions, with only minor socio-ethical implications anticipated.
Environmental sustainability	
AI models	All production models will include extensive logging and version control to maintain transparency and traceability throughout the system lifecycle

6 Conclusion – key takeaways

To conclude, this version of the deliverable establishes the updated trustworthy AI development framework for the AI-PROGNOSIS project. It presents a clear view of trustworthy AI and details how practices are to be operationalized across the AI lifecycle to build trustworthy AI systems. The document also highlights the socio-ethical considerations and their ongoing influence on the design, development, and deployment of the project's AI components. Furthermore, it details the framework components described in Section 4, covering design, data, development, deployment, validation, and monitoring, in alignment with major regulatory and ethical guidelines, including ALTAI, the EU AI Act (2024), EU-MDR, FDA guidance on AI-enabled medical devices, FUTURE-AI international consensus guidelines, and emerging ISO/IEC standards for AI. These components are mapped across the project's AI lifecycle with alignment to the existing guidelines. **Error! Reference source not found.** s summarises the AI-PROGNOSIS components to be followed to ensure that each stage of AI development adheres to the principles of trustworthy AI.

Table 19 AI-PROGNOSIS components aligned with ALTAI requirements for each step in the AI component lifecycle.

AI step	AI-PROGNOSIS component	ALTAI requirement
Design and Specification	Embedding personal autonomy and exercising oversight	HAO
	Explainability tailored to each user	TPR
	Identify fairness goals and protected attributes	DnDF
	Equal access to stakeholders	DnDF
Data Preparation	Outlier detection and data sanitisation	TRS
	Data pseudonymisation or anonymisation	PDG
	Data quality assessment and bias identification (via data distribution metrics)	DnDF
Development and Validation	Training for generalisation (balance between under/ overfitting)	TRS
	Adversarial training and regularisation	TRS
	Performance benchmarking, including reliability assessment	TRS
	Selection of model to enter production based on trade-off between performance and privacy risks	PDG
	Explainable model design	TPR
	Uncertainty benchmarking	TPR
	Assessment and mitigation of bias	DnDF
UX/UI and Deployment	User feedback	HAO
	Adversarial testing	HAO, TRS
	Disclaimers	TRS, PDG, DnDF
	Input data validation	TRS
	Data minimisation	PDG
	Right to be forgotten	PDG

AI step	AI-PROGNOSIS component	ALTAI requirement
	Explanation of models and their outputs	TPR
	Educational content on AI	TPR
	UI/UX best practices and performance optimisation	DnDF
External validation	Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness in clinical studies	TPR, DnDF
Overarching Management and Workflow	Observability for robust clinical data validation	TRS
	End-User assessment of model output explanations in clinical studies	TRS
	Model Operations	TRS, TPR, ACC
Overarching Management and Workflow	Model and dataset reporting	TPR, ACC
	Open models and datasets	TPR, ACC
	Security and GDPR compliance	PDG
	Sustainability and societal impact	SEW
	Risk management system and file	TRS, ACC, PDG

To reinforce the socio-ethical foundation of the AI-PROGNOSIS project, we summarize below the procedural approach taken to ensure alignment with ethical principles, regulatory foresight, and continuous oversight. This summary complements the technical framework and implementation activities described earlier in this deliverable.

Summary of the procedural socio-ethical approach of AI-PROGNOSIS

1. Addressing Relevant Issues via ALTAI

The project uses the ALTAI framework to identify and assess ethical and social issues across its models, with tools developed to ensure measurable and transparent adherence to key principles.

2. Complementary Values Integration

The procedural framework allows the iterative inclusion of ethical values beyond “trustworthiness,” promoting a value-sensitive design. While no novel values emerged during stakeholder engagement so far, the iterative process ensures responsiveness to diverse concerns.

3. Policy Anticipation and Adaptation

AI-PROGNOSIS proactively aligns with evolving policy landscapes, including early adaptation to the EU AI Act. This readiness ensures compliance and positions the project to navigate future regulatory changes.

4. Ethical Oversight Mechanisms

Oversight extends beyond individual models to the entire system, ensuring continuous monitoring and ethical coherence throughout development, deployment, and future use.

Across the AI-PROGNOSIS partners, significant progress has been made in implementing trustworthy AI practices. All partners conducted data quality checks, adopted validation pipelines, and took initial steps toward bias evaluation. Key modelling practices—such as

cross-validation, regularization, and external dataset evaluation—are broadly in place, and explainability is integrated where complex models are used. Security and auditability protocols have been adopted across all partners, with plans for full adherence to reporting standards like TRIPOD-AI. On the UI/UX and deployment side, efforts have emphasized privacy-aware design, data minimization, and user-centric performance optimization.

However, certain elements remain under development, including formal bias and uncertainty quantification (to be detailed in D3.4), integration of adversarial robustness testing, explainability in user interfaces, and systematic collection of user feedback (to be demonstrated in D4.4/D4.5). Future iterations will prioritize these aspects, alongside environmental impact tracking and fairness auditing using dedicated libraries, to ensure full alignment with the AI Act and emerging ISO/IEC standards.

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Appendix I – Trustworthy AI compliance report

Compliance report 1: UX/UI and deployment

Assessment and action plan for UX/UI and Deployment		
Prepared to be filled by	Prepared by	Version - Date

Feedback and Implementation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please provide details on how each of the below steps has been implemented. <i>If certain steps have not been implemented, what is the plan for addressing these areas in future iterations?</i> • Include any planned future steps or improvements in these areas to ensure ongoing compliance with trustworthy AI principles.

1. UX/UI and Deployment
a. User Feedback
Have you implemented mechanisms for collecting user feedback on the AI model’s outputs? If yes, describe the method (e.g., explicit feedback via forms, implicit feedback via user behaviour logs).
...
How will the user feedback be processed and used to improve model performance or application usability?
...
b. Adversarial Testing
Are you planning to conduct any adversarial testing (e.g., using the Adversarial Robustness Toolbox) to evaluate the robustness of the model or interface? If yes, what are your plans to integrate adversarial testing?
...
c. Input Data Validation
What mechanisms will be put in place to validate user input integrity (e.g., completeness checks, standardized multiple-choice forms)?
...
d. Data Minimisation
What data minimisation practices will you apply in your UI/UX design (e.g., limiting input fields to necessary data)?
...
e. Right to Be Forgotten
Will you be implementing a mechanism that allows users to request deletion of their personal data?
...
What is the procedure and expected timeline for processing erasure requests?
...

f. Explanation of Models and Their Outputs
Have you integrated explainability components in your UI (e.g., SHAP, LIME visualizations)?
...
How will you present the different models' decisions and uncertainty to end-users (e.g., visual reports, textual summaries)?
...
g. Educational Content on AI
Will you be including educational content to explain how the AI system works to users? If yes, what educational elements are planned to be given?
...
h. UI/UX Best Practices and Performance Optimisation
What UI/UX guidelines were followed during the app development as the design basis (e.g., Google's Material Design, Apples's Human Interface Guidelines)?
...
Have you considered accessibility features (e.g., colour contrast, font sizes)?
...
What steps have been taken to ensure performance optimisation (e.g., reducing loading times, limiting data transmission)?
...
Were UI/UX choices validated via co-creation sessions or user testing?
...
i. Any additional info you want to add
...

Compliance report 2: Model development

Assessment and action plan for model development		
Prepared to be filled by	Prepared by	Date

Feedback and Implementation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please provide details on how each of the below steps has been implemented. <i>If certain steps have not been implemented, what is the plan for addressing these areas in future iterations?</i> Include any planned future steps or improvements in these areas to ensure ongoing compliance with trustworthy AI principles.

1. Data Preparation
a. Data Quality and Bias:
How did you assess the quality of the data used in the model? <i>If not, what is the plan to assess data quality in future iterations?</i>

...
What steps have been taken to identify and mitigate bias in the training dataset? <i>If none, what strategies will be implemented to address potential biases moving forward?</i>
...
b. Outlier Detection and Data Sanitization:
Which mechanisms did you implement for outlier detection in the dataset? <i>If not, how do you plan to address outliers in future data processing?</i>
...
What data sanitization methods have been applied to ensure data integrity? <i>If none, what is the plan to ensure data integrity in upcoming data cycles?</i>
...
c. Data Privacy:
Have you applied data pseudonymization or anonymization techniques to protect user privacy? <i>If yes, explain how. If not, what steps will you take to implement data privacy protections in the future?</i>
...
d. Protected Variables:
How have you identified and managed protected variables (e.g., gender, race) in the dataset to ensure fairness? <i>If not managed, what steps will you take to identify and handle these variables in the next phase?</i>
...
2. Development & Internal Validation
a. Model Training and Generalization:
What steps have been taken to ensure the model generalizes well to unseen data? <i>If not, how do you plan to enhance the model's generalization in future iterations?</i>
...
Have you conducted any adversarial training or regularization to enhance robustness? <i>If not, what are the future plans for adversarial training or regularization?</i>
...
b. Performance Benchmarking:
Have you established performance benchmarks for the model? <i>If not, what is the plan to set performance benchmarks in the future?</i>
...
What metrics did you use to assess the performance of your model? <i>If no metrics were used, how do you plan to incorporate performance metrics going forward?</i>
...
Have you assessed the model's robustness? <i>If yes, what metrics did you use for this assessment? If not, what future steps will you take to assess and improve model robustness?</i>
...
c. Bias Assessment and Mitigation:

Have you assessed the model for biases during development? What fairness metrics did you use? <i>If not assessed, what are the plans to conduct bias assessment and mitigation in future developments?</i>
...
Did you use any specific fairness libraries or frameworks (e.g., IBM AI Fairness 360, Fairlearn) during bias mitigation? <i>If not, what frameworks or tools will you consider using in the future for bias mitigation?</i>
...
d. Explainable Model Design:
Is the developed model inherently explainable, and if so, how does it provide explanations for its predictions?
...
Are there post-hoc explainability methods in place for interpreting the model's decisions? <i>If none, what is the plan to implement post-hoc explainability methods?</i>
...
e. Uncertainty Benchmarking:
Have you conducted uncertainty benchmarking to evaluate the reliability of the model's predictions? <i>If not, what strategies will you adopt to manage uncertain predictions?</i>
...
f. Protected Variables in model training:
How will you integrate the chosen protected variables into model development to ensure that they are properly considered during training and evaluation, and what steps will you take to prevent the model's predictions from disproportionately impacting any protected group?
...
3. Overarching Management and Workflow
a. Model and Dataset Reporting:
Have you used mechanisms such as the TRIPOD checklist for comprehensive reporting of model and dataset characteristics? <i>If not, what is the plan to incorporate comprehensive reporting mechanisms?</i>
...
b. Security:
How do you ensure the security of the model and data throughout its lifecycle, including aspects like data encryption, access control, secure storage, and monitoring for potential threats? <i>If not secured, what steps will be taken to enhance security in future implementations?</i>
...
c. Societal Impact:
What potential socio-ethical implications might the developed model have, particularly regarding its impact on work, skills, and society at large?
...
Are you using methods to reduce the environmental impact of your AI operations, such as selecting eco-friendly cloud providers like Hetzner, or planning to include a report on the socio-ethical implications of your tools as part of your development process? <i>If not, what future steps will you take to minimize environmental impact?</i>
...

d. Auditability and Accountability:

Have you implemented specific mechanisms to facilitate the AI system's auditability, such as detailed logging, version control, or third-party audits? If yes, which mechanisms have you used? *If not, what mechanisms do you plan to implement to ensure auditability and accountability?*

...